

MASTER THESIS

A COST EFFECTIVE KITE STATE ESTIMATOR FOR RELIABLE CONTROL OF KITES

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Embedded Systems Architecture

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**A Cost-Effective Kite State Estimator for Reliable
Automatic Control of Kites**

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Hereby I declare that I wrote this thesis myself with the help of no more than the mentioned literature and auxiliary means.

Berlin, 28.05.2012

.....
(Johannes Peschel)

Abstract

Airborne Wind Energy (AWE) is a developing technology that uses tethered wings to harvest wind energy and convert it into electrical energy. Most of the AWE concepts that will be presented in this thesis have one common challenge: Estimating the position and the orientation of the kite, also called kite state, especially during highly dynamic flight situations. The focus of this thesis is first, to investigate, if angular sensors are feasible to obtain reliable position data and second, which fusion algorithm can be used to join the data of the angular and Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) sensors. The TU Delft prototype is a suitable testing platform for this purpose.

The author added angular sensors to the ground station of the TU Delft AWE system that measure the elevation and the horizontal displacement of the tether holding the kite. They are mounted on a modular stainless steel construction, which has low wear and a long lifetime. The author used the tether length and the angular data to obtain a new position. This position was merged with the two GNSS positions that were already attached to the kite. The angular sensors were able to measure with a resolution of $<0.01^\circ$. The elevation and azimuth position of the kite had an error of less than 0.7° as long as the tether force was higher than 2000N. One of the GNSS sensors provided reliable data during low force phases. A reliable position in all flight conditions could be obtained by using double exponential smoothing prediction to merge both positions. This development enables the implementation of a reliable kite power control system.

Zusammenfassung

Flugwindenergie (engl. Airborne Wind Energy (AWE)) ist eine aufkommende Technologie, die mit leinengebundenen Drachen Windkraft in elektrische Energie umsetzt. Die meisten AWE Konzepte, die in dieser Arbeit vorgestellt werden, haben eine gemeinsame Herausforderung: die Positions- und Orientierungsbestimmung, auch genannt 'kite state', ganz besonders in hochdynamischen Flugsituationen. Die Schwerpunkte dieser Arbeit sind erstens, die Prüfung, ob Winkelsensoren für eine verlässliche Positionsbestimmung brauchbar sind, und zweitens, welcher Fusionsalgorithmus für eine Verschmelzung von Winkelsensordaten und globalen Navigationssatellitensystemdaten (GNSS) genutzt werden kann. Der Prototyp der TU Delft ist eine passende Testplattform für diesen Zweck.

Der Autor fügte zu der Bodenstation des TU Delft AWE Systems Winkelsensoren hinzu, die den Höhenwinkel und die horizontale Auslenkung der Leine messen. Diese sind auf einer modular aufgebauten, rostfreien Stahlkonstruktion angebracht, die wenig Reibung und eine lange Lebensdauer besitzt. Der Autor nutzte die Leinenlänge und die Winkeldaten, um eine neue Position zu ermitteln. Diese Position wurde mit zwei GNSS Positionsdaten verschmolzen, die bereits am Drachen der TU Delft vorhanden waren. Die Winkelsensoren haben eine Messgenauigkeit von $<0,01^\circ$. Der Erhebungswinkel und der Horizontalwinkel haben einen Fehler von weniger als $0,7^\circ$, solange die Kraft auf die Leine mehr als 2000N beträgt. Bei geringer Kraft liefert ein GNSS Sensor eine verlässliche Position. Durch die Verwendung von 'Double Exponential Smoothing Prediction' (DESP) zur Verbindung dieser beiden Positionen konnte in allen Flugsituationen eine verlässliche Position gewonnen werden. Diese Entwicklung ermöglicht die Umsetzung eines verlässlichen Kontrollsystems für Drachenenergie.

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Nomenclature

$(lat, long, alt)_k$ Latitude, longitude and altitude position of the kite in world geodetic coordinates

ω_k	Angular momentum of the kite (roll, pitch, yaw)	[rad/s]
ϕ	Azimuth angle	[rad]
θ	Elevation angle	[rad]
A	Area	[m^2]
a_k	Acceleration of the kite	[m/s^2]
B	Magnetic field	[$mGauss$]
F_a	Aerodynamic force	[N]
$F_{t,g}$	Line (tether) force at the ground station	[N]
$F_{t,k}$	Line (tether) force at the KCU	[N]
f_t	Force factor at time t	[–]
I	Current	[A]
L/D	Lift over Drag equals to c_L/c_D	[–]
l_t	Tether length	[rad]
P_w	Wind Power Density	[kW/m^2]
$p_{static,k}$	Static pressure at the kite	[kPa]
r	radius of Sphere	[m]
T	Temperature	[C]
U	Voltage	[V]
U_p	Voltage of the power potentiometer in the KCU	[V]
U_s	Voltage of the steering potentiometer	[V]
v_a	Apparrent wind velocity	[m/s]
v_w	Windspeed	[m/s]
$v_{a,k}$	Apparrent wind velocity experianced by the kite	[m/s]

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v_t	Tether speed	[m/s]
$v_{w,k}$	Wind speed at the ground	[m/s]
AoA	Angle of attack of a wing in an airflow	
ARC-EG	Horizontal Arc , Vertical Arc and Kite Distance coordinate system in EG reference frame ($r\phi, r\theta, r$)	
DESP	Double Exponential Smoothing Prediction	
E	Estimator, also referred to as estimated trajectory and estimated kite in the simulation	
EAK-EG	Elevation-Azimuth-Kite coordinate system in EG reference frame (ϕ, θ, r)	
Flygen	AWE concepts with generator on the flying device	
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System	
GPS	Global Positioning System	
Groundgen	AWE concepts with generator at the ground	
KCU	Kite Control Unit	
LEI	Leading Edge Inflatable Kite, also called tube kite	
posARC-EG	Position in ARC-EG coordinates.	
rad	Degrees in radian	
T	Trimble sensor, also referred to as Trimble trajectory and Trimble kite in the simulation	
X	Xsens sensor, also referred to as XSens trajectory and XSens kite in the simulation	

1 Introduction

1.1 Why Airborne Wind Energy (AWE)

Global Energy consumption will rise dramatically and the share of renewable energy will grow. Global energy consumption has risen from 354 quadrillion Btu in 1990 to 505 in 2008 and it is projected by Conti and Holtberg (2011), that the need will be as much as 770 Btu until 2035. This means that the need of energy in 2035 is twice as big as 1990 and 85% more than in 2008. According to the central scenario of Birol (2012), published by IEA, the share of coal, oil and gas falls from 81% in 2010 to 75% until 2035 while, in the same time, renewable energies rise from 20% to 31%. Also, electrical energy grows in the same period by 70% to an annual demand of 32000 TWh by 2035. This states that the global energy market is vastly growing with a trend from fossil to renewable energies, which is only achievable with increasing subsidies. The rapid growth of subsidies for renewable energies from \$88 billion in 2011 (24% more than 2010) to \$240 billion in 2035 may seem a lot but comparing it to the fact that subsidies for fossil fuels were \$523 billion in 2011 puts that amount into perspective. This trend is in deed desirable for the whole global ecosystem. Nowadays, the climate change and the global warming is a commonly known and accepted fact (see Meinshausen et al. (2009)). Further, the two-degree goal of the global climate policy is hard to accomplish and demands low-carbon technologies. In the rather optimistic Efficient World Scenario of Birol (2012), *“the energy related CO₂ emissions peak before 2020 and decline to 30.5Gt, pointing to a long-term average of 3°C.”* To be able to fulfill the energy requirements of the future, it is of major importance to invest in the development and research of renewable energies.

Wind Energy is one of the biggest growing renewable sources of energy. The World Energy Outlook estimates 25% growth in non-OECD countries and 47% in OECD countries until 2035. According to Birol (2012), other renewable energies will also grow by 16% (bio energy), 15% (solar power) and 11% (hydro) in OECD countries. Clearly, this indicates that wind energy will play a big role in renewable energies and will become a big part in the global energy mix. Wind turbines already play an important role, but they have two major disadvantages. On the one hand the *“[...] operating costs of wind turbines are much lower than the operation costs for fossil fuel-fired power plants, but the high construction costs make the total cost per kilowatt hour higher”* Bosch (2012). On the other hand, wind power can only be harvested when there is actually wind, which causes peaks in the energy generation. A planned energy mix or storage technologies are helpful to overcome this drawback.

Airborne Wind Energy with Kites is a new way of harvesting wind energy without the disadvantages of wind turbines. It could be the answer to the future demand for renewable energy. It is a fast growing research area and many different kite based AWE concepts have been developed, especially over the last decade (see Fagiano and Milanese (2012)). The kite

1 Introduction

power research group of the section wind energy of the Delft University of Technology is one of these research groups and has grown into a major hub and a knowledge center for AWE. Its demonstrator, which can be seen in Fig. 1.1, has an 20kW generator on the ground that uses kites from 6 m^2 to 25 m^2 for a cycle based energy production. The system runs with an autopilot, which steers the kite automatically, keeping it on the desired track. But since it is a new technology, many challenges have to be faced.

Fig. 1.1: TU Delft AWE Demonstrator

For example, the autopilot works fine, if it receives consistent position data from the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) sensor at the kite. However, in highly dynamic situations, this sensor loses track and delivers wrong data. So, to improve the position data, an alternative way of measuring the kite position is desirable. Fusing positions from different sensors leads to a robust, redundant and reliable system. In case of failure of one sensor, e.g. the American Global Positioning System (GPS) fails or is shut down, the kite power system can still operate.

Having a lot of high-tech sensors is advantageous, but at the same time it is very expensive and sensitive to environmental impacts. A low cost sensors in addition to a high performance GPS sensor would increase the accuracy of the position data significantly while keeping the systems costs relatively low. The kite state includes velocity, orientation and position. There are multiple ways to enhance the kite state with accurate position data. Other research groups use tether angles and tether length to determine the position of the flying device. Therefore, angular sensors in combination with sensors, that measure the tether length at the ground are ideal candidates to create a cheap, reliable and durable position estimation system. A position could be estimated based on the kite distance kd , its elevation ϕ and azimuth angle θ , as it is shown in Fig. 1.2.

1.2 Objectives

The recent section described the need for a reliable position estimation for the TU Delft kite power system. The first objective is to extend the TU Delft system with angular sensors that measure the elevation and the azimuth of the tether at the winch. This information shall be used to get an additional kite position by combining it with the tether length. Further

Fig. 1.2: Kite positioning based on elevation, azimuth and tether length (Jehle (2012))

this data will be fused with already existing GNSS data to create a more reliable kite state. Afterwards, it will be investigated, if the position is sufficiently accurate and reliable to be able to operate in autopilot mode. As a conclusion, different kite state estimators are introduced and a recommendation will be given about sensors that shall be used for reliable position estimation depending on the desired size and cost of the AWE system.

1.3 Structure

Chapter 2 gives an overview about current AWE concepts. It also gives an overview about current autopilot approaches and tether models. An economic analysis of the current system is presented. It shows different kite positioning methods and a comparison of sensors for angular measurement. The chapter also enlightens the reader about different algorithms that can be used for sensor fusing.

Chapter 3 shows the approach and fundamental concepts that are important to meet the objectives. It includes requirements and design decisions of the sensors that are used to measure the elevation and azimuth angle. It also describes the fusing algorithm that is used for the kite state, which includes an estimated position based on GNSS and angular sensors.

Chapter 4 contains the hardware design. Firstly, it points out the design of the arm that follows the tether for elevation measurement and the applied mechanics to measure the azimuth. It describes the computational hardware that was used to access and post process the measurement data. Finally, the implementation section describes how the hardware is mounted and connected.

Chapter 5 introduces the final software structure. An explanation about design decisions that let to the software components shows the background of the resulting software structure, data flow and functionalities. The chapter closes with the implementation specification.

The test results are summarized in Chapter 6. This includes firstly, a test of the angular sensors and an analysis of the tether dynamics. Secondly, simulated tests of the kite state Estimator and last but not least, the results of the field-test on the 21st of January of 2013.

A summary and outlook in Chapter 7 complete this thesis.

2 Fundamentals and Related Work

This chapter gives an overview about the current state of the art. It starts with a review on AWE basics and continues with a detailed description of the TU Delft AWE system. Next, economic aspects of the system are discussed and current autopilot approaches, kite positioning methods and tether models are presented. Finally, an overview and comparison about sensors for angular measurement is given and different fusing algorithms are introduced.

2.1 Airborne Wind Energy

Airborne Wind Energy is a new type of wind energy generation, which has the potential to overcome the two major problems of wind turbines, which are high production costs and limited capacity factor (see 1.1). The main concept of airborne wind energy is to have a flying device that is connected to the ground with a line, string or tether. This reduces the mass of the system significantly, which makes AWE systems easier to deploy in remote areas, mountains and offshore. The second advantage of a tethered flying device towards a generator on a tower, is, that the tether allows the AWE system to harvest wind energy at higher altitudes (see Aglietti (2009)). Fig. 2.1b shows the operational height of wind turbines and AWE. But why is it better to go higher for wind power generation?

The Wind Power Density P_w defines the maximum power output from wind in $\frac{kW}{m^2}$ as defined by Loyd (1980). It can be calculated with the following formula:

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho_{air} v_{wind}^3 \quad (2.1)$$

Eq. 2.1 shows a cubic relationship between wind speed and P_w . Respectively, doubling the wind speed results in an eight times higher power output. Further, Fig. 2.1a shows the average wind speed over altitude in the Netherlands. The friction of the earth's surface makes the wind slow and gusty close to the ground, whereas the wind gets stronger and more constant in higher altitudes, hence P_w rises (see Archer and Caldeira (2009)). Fig. 2.1a shows nicely how the average wind speed increases with altitude: it rises significantly up to one kilometer, then the curve buckles while the wind speed still keeps on rising until over ten km until it starts to drop again. Fig. 2.1b shows P_w up to two km height and illustrates the significant increase of possible power output related to the height of the wing which collects the power. It also shows that the desirable operational altitude for AWE reaches from 500m to 1000m and that the current height of wind turbines, which is about 100m. According to Archer and Caldeira (2009), this is a global phenomenon. Therefore, the second disadvantage, the limited capacity factor of wind turbines caused by too low wind speeds, is contained by the fact, that a higher average wind speed boosts the operational time of AWE systems while also reducing the cost per kWh. Higher P_w allows producing more energy with the same wing size. Although it is theoretically possible to compete with wind turbines and other energy production methods, many challenges have to be faced. None of the AWE concepts is ready

Fig. 2.1: High altitude wind in the Netherlands (Schmehl (2013))

for mass production yet. Especially in the area of automatic launch and landing, lifetime of tether and wing (kite), and flight permits.

2.2 AWE concepts

The main advantages of AWE towards conventional wind turbines have been explained in the recent paragraph. Many different research groups (40 in 2011) focus on systems that can harvest wind energy in high altitudes (Schmehl (2013); Fagiano and Milanese (2012)).

There are some systems with a generator at the ground (Groundgen), where aerodynamic force is delivered to the ground through the tether and this mechanical energy is converted into electrical energy. Alternatively, the electrical energy can also be generated on the flying device (Flygen) transmitting electrical energy to the ground through a wire in the tether. Makani (2013) uses a rigid wing with four propellers to produce energy.

Fig. 2.2: Makani Wind Power Wing (Makani (2013))

The energy generation here is similar to a horizontal wind turbine, the propellers are connected to a generator and the rotation creates electrical energy with induction, similar to a dynamo.

But how can the power be produced when the generator is at the ground?

Well established prototype systems are these of Bormann (2013) and the kite power research group around Schmehl (2013) at the Technical University of Delft. They both produce energy in cycles by varying the tether length. One cycle consists of two parts. The first part is the power generation phase, where the wing is flying a figure of eight at low elevation angle

Fig. 2.3: Pumping Cycle of AWE Groundgen systems. Power generation during reel out (left) and reeling depowered kite back in (right) using a kite as wing (Schmehl (2012))

and high angle of attack (AoA) (Fig. 2.3, left). This guarantees maximum aerodynamic force. The tether reels slowly out during this mode of operation. The tether is rolled on a drum that is connected to a generator. Reeling out creates a circular motion of the drum that drives the generator. At a defined maximum tether length, the wing depowers (low AoA) and the tether is reeled back in (Fig. 2.3, right). By increasing the elevation angle, the kite flies closer to the zenith and out of the power zone (see Fig. 2.4a). Fig. 2.4b shows a complete pumping cycle of a kite power system: the reel out phase in the power zone and the reel in phase close to the zenith.

(a) Wind window of a tethered wing. The area of action is a quarter sphere. The power depend on the azimuth and elevation angle (+/-) (Furey and Harvey (2008))

(b) Complete pumping cycle with kite (Vlugt et al. (2013))

Fig. 2.4: Power zones and pumping cycle

The second part needs energy, but the reel out phase produces approximately 10 times more energy than the reel in phase needs (see Fig. 2.5). The main difference between the systems of EnerKite and TU Delft is the number of tethers. Having more than one line induces more drag and reduces the efficiency of the system (see Argatov et al. (2011)). Nevertheless, all systems above use fast moving wings for energy production, which has another advantage towards wind turbines. Looking at Eq. 2.2 for the power output (derived from Loyd (1980)), one can see that the mechanical power output P of the system rises with the apparent wind velocity v_a :

Fig. 2.5: Mechanical power production during 5 pumping cycles (Schmehl (2013))

$$P = P_w A \frac{v_a^2 v_t}{v_w^2 v_w} \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{\left(\frac{L}{D}\right)^2}} \quad (2.2)$$

Assuming the area of the wing A , wind speed v_w , and reel out speed v_t as well as $\frac{L}{D}$ of the wing are constant, the power output is quadratic proportional to v_a . The apparent wind speed is proportional to the speed of the kite, meaning the faster the wing moves, the higher the power output. This correlation is explored and summarized by Ockels et al. (2006), Terink (2009) and de Groot et al. (2011).

This is the reason, why 50% of the power of a wind turbine is generated by the 25% outmost part of its wing (see Schmehl (2013)) because the speed of the wingtips is the fastest. Therefore, the power output per m^2 of a tethered kite would be comparable to a wind turbine on a one km high tower with the whole blade having the same speed as the blade tips (see Fig. 2.6). This is the theory, but in reality, the $\frac{L}{D}$, which is also an important

Fig. 2.6: Wind turbines and AWE concept (Schmehl (2013))

factor of P_w , is much higher for wind turbine blades than it is for AWE wings, especially for

kites. Nevertheless, the theoretical benefit shows that AWE concepts can bring wind energy production to new heights. The following explains the AWE generator of the TU Delft. To get more information about AWE concepts, please look at Fagiano and Milanese (2012).

2.3 TU Delft System Description

The TU Delft AWE system is a Groundgen concept with a flexible tube kite as a wing. Fig. 2.7 shows an overview of the TU Delft kite power system. The following paragraph explains the main system components, which can be seen in Fig. 2.7.

Fig. 2.7: Complete system overview (Vlugt et al. (2013))

The Kite (location: 1 in Fig. 2.7) is the wing that collects the aerodynamic force. The

Fig. 2.8: Different kite wings

current kite (beginning 2013) is a 25 m^2 Leading Edge Inflatable (LEI) kite. This type is also called tube kite, because its shape is defined by inflatable tubes at the front (front tube) and at the hydrofoil (struts) (see Fig. 2.8a). Other types of wing structures have been tested, such as a kite plane, which is an inflatable plane like structure (Fig. 2.8c). A ram air kite (also called soft kite) is a double membrane structure that gets inflated by v_a through inlets at the

leading edge (Fig. 2.8b). Tab. 2.1 shows the ad- and disadvantages of different wing types. One of the main reasons, according to DeWachter (2012), why the TU Delft has decided to use a LEI kite is its higher depower capability in comparison to RAM air kites.

LEI (2.8a)	Ram-Air (2.8b)	Kite plane (2.8c)	Rigid wing (2.2)
high depower, light, transportable	good aerodynamic properties, light, transportable	theoretically good aerodynamic properties, light, transportable	good aerodynamic properties, long lifetime
short lifetime	low depower, short lifetime	flapping increases drag	big, heavy

Tab. 2.1: Kite types

The Bridle Line System (location: 2 in Fig. 2.7) is the connecting element between the main tether, the Kite Control Unit (KCU) and the kite. It is necessary to steer, depower and to support the shape of the kite. The lines that are attached to the leading edge of the kite hold the kite in its shape. Most part of the aerodynamic force F_a at the ground comes from these lines, which are directly connected to the main tether. Two lines, at the left and right wingtips of the kite are used by the KCU to steer and depower the kite.

Fig. 2.9: Bridle line system (left, Jehle (2012)) and KCU (right, Schmehl (2013))

The KCU (location: 3 in Fig. 2.7) is a characteristic feature of the TU Delft AWE system. Having a control unit close to the kite makes the one tether design possible, which reduces drag and costs. The kite also reacts faster to steering inputs from the KCU compared to steering inputs from the ground. The KCU includes a steering winch, which is connected to both steering lines so that a rotation causes one line to be pulled, and the other one being released. This design makes it possible to steer with very low forces, because both lines are in equilibrium. The depower winch is connected to both steering lines of the kite, which allows to change the length of both lines simultaneously. Making the back lines longer will depower the kite and decreases the AoA, while shorten them will increase the AoA and power the kite. A servo brake blocks the depower winch, so that no power consumption at constant depower settings.

The Tether is a 4mm thick 1000m long Dyneema SK75 cable, which is very light ($9,1 \cdot 10^{-3} \frac{kg}{m}$) while still having a high breaking strength (13,5 kN). At the top end, the tether is equipped with a weak link, which brakes in case F_a gets too high (see Schmehl (2013)).

The Ground Station (location: 4 in Fig. 2.7) has a generator of 20kW nominal power. A spindle motor rolls the tether evenly on the drum. The generator can reel the tether in and out at a maximum speed v_t of $8 \frac{m}{s}$. It has a 20 kWh LiFePO4 battery to store the produced energy. The ground station converts the mechanical energy to electrical energy and controls tether force and the reel in/out speed.

2.4 Economical Aspects of the Kite Power System

To make a pumping kite power system economically competitive with wind turbines, other renewable energies and conventional energies, several scenarios are possible. For industrial use, creating huge wind parks with scaled up systems and kite sizes of $100 m^2$ and more are imaginable. For such a system, the critical part and the biggest cost factor is the lifetime of materials: especially the kite and the tether (Kirkenier (2012)). Therefore, expensive GNSS sensors can be used and redundant sensors are wanted to increase the reliability and safety of the system. Because the influence of the sensor costs on the total system costs is lower for larger units.

On the other hand, small-scale systems are also possible. The mobility and small size and weight of such a system is beneficial when being used as a mobile generator wherever power is needed and no supply network is available, e.g. in crisis zones, developing countries, after environmental impacts and small islands. For such systems, a robust and cheap sensor environment is required. The sensor environment depends on the size of the system and the desired level of reliability, robustness, service period and lifetime. More sensors and high-performance GPS sensors increase the reliability and safety of a system while increasing the production costs. Low-tech sensors (e.g. angular potentiometers) increase the robustness of the system and can decrease the costs. Using fewer sensors decreases the reliability and safety of the system.

2.5 Control Algorithms

The kite and the winch are automated with control algorithms. The reel out speed is controlled using F_t . Different autopilots were implemented in the TU Delft kite power prototype. The autopilots for the kite need the position and the orientation. Some also need the wind direction and velocity, as well as tether length l_t . The earliest autopilot defines four way-points for the kite that define the trajectory for the kite. The latest autopilot controls the kite based on an ideal trajectory, which is defined on the unit sphere. The position of the kite is projected to the unit sphere. The length of the lot from the projected position to the ideal trajectory defines the intensity of the steering input for the kite. A kite which is further away from the ideal trajectory gets a stronger steering input than a kite which is closer.

2.6 Kite State

This section describes the sensors that are used to measure and calculate the kite state. It enlightens the reader about drawbacks and benefits of different sensors and illustrates background of design decisions. Special focus will be on kite position estimation which was found to be a major challenge. Tab. 2.2 groups the most important sensors based on their usage in the TU Delft prototype system of beginning 2013.

Use		Sensor type	Output
Position, Orientation	1	XSens MTi-G	$(lat, long, alt)_k, a_k, \omega_k, B, p_{static,k}$
	1	Trimble GNSS	$(lat, long, alt)_k, v_k, a_k$
	2	Unilog GPS	$(lat, long, alt)_k$
	3	Winch GPS	$(lat, long, alt)_k$
Steering, Depower	3	Steering potentiometer	Relative left steering value (0-100%)
	3	Depower potentiometer	Relative power (0-100%)
Wind Speed	2	Pitot tube	$v_{a,k}$
	5	Ultrasonic wind sensor	$v_{w,g}, T$
Monitoring	3 & 4	Miscellaneous	T, U, I
	3 & 4	Load cell	$F_{t,k}, F_{t,g}$
	4	Incremental Encoder	v_t, l_t

Tab. 2.2: Sensors of the TU Delft Kitepower system beginning 2013 (see 2.7 for sensor positions, from Vlugt et al. (2013))

Actual Steering and Depower Settings are measured in the KCU. The relative left steering value from 0% to 100% (0%: maximum left turn; 50%: no steering; 100%: maximum right turn) and relative power a.k.a. AoA from 0% to 100% (0%: min. power, min AoA, max. depower; 100%: max. power, max. AoA, min. depower) is calculated from the voltage output U_p and U_s of analogue potentiometers attached to the steering and depower winches.

The Wind Speed is measured by the Ultrasonic wind sensor on the ground, which delivers temperature and the ground wind vector $v_{w,g}$ in 6 m height, parallel to the earth surface and relative to the magnetic north. It is located on a beam upwind from the ground station. The pitot tube in the bridle of the kite can move freely and will align itself to the wind, it measures $v_{a,k}$ as a scalar.

Monitoring is important for detecting malfunctions and knowing the electrical power in- and outputs. Current I and voltage U give indications about the status of steering and depower motors and the batteries of the KCU. Temperature, U and I is measured at the spindle motor, main generator and each battery cell in the ground station. The tether force $F_{t,g}$ is needed to control the reel out speed v_t of the line, for position estimation and to get the mechanical power output of the system.

The Position is determined by two Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) systems. The Trimble sensor is based on GPS and GLONASS satellite frequencies, whereas the XSense sensor is based on GPS only. The XSense internal measurement unit (IMU) is located on the main strut of the kite. It comes with four other sensors that allow sensor fusing using a Kalman filter (see Welch et al. (2006); Xsens Technologies B.V. (2011)). Tests concluded that the position, which is estimated by the XSense, is not always correct. In case of lost satellite connections and in many other situations, where no pattern could be determined, the position of the XSense IMU is very wrong. According to the test on 18.03.2012 (4.8m/s wind speed), the result of the Kalman filter, which tries to guess a prediction based on the integration of the accelerometer and gyroscope, leads to obviously wrong data and takes up to 10s to produce meaningful data after regaining GPS connection. A correlation between this error and kinetic momentum was found. The reason why the XSense produces sometimes but not always faulty data during highly dynamic situations like a figure of eight was not further investigated. This is due to the fact, that the IMU is delivered as a black box and the parameters of the Kalman filter can not be changed. Four different systems to measure the position were tested and implemented by Marien Ruppert to find out if this is a general GNSS/ GPS problem.

The sensors that were used are:

- XSense Mti-G IMU
- SM Modelbau GPS logger
- Genie GT-31 GPS
- QStraz BT-1300 GPS

A conspicuous correlation between the accelerations and the difference can be regarded. The results of this internal report from Ruppert and Jehle (2013) show that the sensors position difference was 10m to 80m during highly dynamic flight and 1m to 5m during the reel in phase. A reliable determination of the kite position is desirable. Therefore the Trimble high performance GPS sensor was added to the system, which is able to cope with accelerations up to 8g. It was tested on the 24th of April 2012 (3.9 m/s wind speed). The tether length gives a reliable indication about the real position of the kite and makes a statement about the quality of the results possible. Elongation and tether sag were neglected and the GPS tether length was calculated by taking the distance between the kite and the ground station GPS locations. Fig. 2.10 shows that the quality of the Trimble GPS with a mean error of 0.1 cm and a standard deviation of 3.07 m is much better than the XSense with a mean error of 4.5 m and a standard deviation of 15.4 m.

Although the Trimble shows better performance it still loses track during high changes of kinetic moments. Fig. 2.11 shows the position of the kite during a figure of eight as seen on by an observer at the ground station. One can see that the position is faulty at the end of two down moving maneuvers (marked with arrows). According to the video of the test day and the steering inputs, the kite flew a smooth curve, whereas the Trimble GPS trajectory has a big dent. The location of each dent is at the end of a downward turn when the acceleration and speed are at a local maximum. The need for a reliable determination of the position remains.

Fig. 2.10: Trimble, XSense and Pitot GPS (Ruppert and Jehle (2013))

2.7 Other positioning Methods

For reliable automatic control, no matter which control algorithm is being used (Section 2.5), it is necessary to have reliable and consistent position. As shown in the previous section, the drawbacks of GPS as it is now cannot be ignored. This chapter shall give an overview about different methods for Kite State estimation.

Optical tracking is one opportunity. Mounting one or more cameras at the ground can be used to determine the position and maybe the orientation of the kite. Pre investigations concluded that it is rather hard to detect a moving object in different light conditions. Using HSV instead of RGB color space makes moving object detections less sensible to light conditions but to track a kite in 1000m distance would most likely need high definition (HD). Making digital image processing on HD images is very expensive (see Gonzalez and Richard (2002)). A possibility would be to have light emitters at the kite that point towards the ground station as suggested by Mehling (2006). This could be LED lights between 300 nm and 400 nm wavelengths, because there is low absorption by the atmosphere (Fig. 2.12).

Fig. 2.11: Figure of eight during autopilot flight (Ruppert and Jehle (2013))

Fig. 2.12: Absorptivity of gases (Nese et al. (1996))

Galileo is Europe's answer to the American GPS, Russian GLONASS and Chinese Compass. Although it is supposed to be more accurate than other satellite navigation solutions (see Benedicto et al. (2000)), it is likely that it has the same problems that GPS has during highly dynamic situations.

Differential GPS has a local fix point at the ground which corrects the GPS position (see Vu et al. (2012)). It is more accurate than normal GPS.

The Heading and the Kite Distance could also be used to determine the position. The fact that the kite is connected to the ground by the tether forces the kite to fly in a half sphere with a radius of the kite distance. Assuming that the kite has a fixed and known AoA, the position can theoretically be determined with the heading and kite distance of the kite. There is only one place on the half sphere, for every possible heading of the kite. A realistic tether model can be used to calculate the kite distance and the heading based on l_t and the orientation of the kite.

Tether Angles and Kite Distance is a way to determine the position of the kite. As shown in Fig. 1.2, the kite distance kd , elevation ϕ and azimuth θ angles can be used to determine the kite position. The problem is, that the tether is influenced by aerodynamic and gravitational forces that cause the angles that are measured at the ground to be different to the real angles as it is shown in Fig. 2.13. The physical basics can be found in Serway and Jewett (2009), the aerodynamic principles in Schlichting and Truckenbrodt (2000) and

the best source for forces on a tether is Aglietti (2009). The drag force that is induced to the tether can be calculated as:

$$D = \frac{1}{2} \rho_{air} v_{a,t}^2 c_D A, \quad (2.3)$$

Fig. 2.13: Drag and gravity on the tether

where D is the total drag force on the tether, ρ_{air} the air pressure, A the projected area of the tether and c_D the drag coefficient of the tether. It can be spitted into a horizontal and a vertical component. This displacement causes that the angles that are measured at the ground ϕ^* , ψ^* differ from the angles of a straight line to the kite ϕ , ψ . Also, the kite distance differs from the tether length l_t . Appropriate models can compensate and correct the effects of drag and gravity.

2.8 Tether Models

In the past, several tether models have been developed. The longer, the thicker and the heavier the tether gets, the more sag and drag is induced to the tether (see Eq. 2.3). The elongation of the tether makes it a complex and a not straightforward task to create a appropriate model. Due to the non-linear behavior of the tether, most models divide the tether in to smaller elements.

The Rigid Tether Model is the simplest way to model a tether. The tether is assumed to be a straight line. It is described by Diehl (2001), Houska (2007), Houska and Diehl (2007) and Ilzhöfer (2007).

The Linear Spring Damper Model represents the tether as an array of springs as described in Baayen (2011). It simulates the tether and its dynamics already quite well for a tether with high tensioning force F_t and a length of less than 100m.

The Lumped Masses Model is an extended spring damper model. It has more degrees of freedom caused by the addition of masses at the connection points of two springs. For more information see Baayen (2011) and Jehle (2012).

Discretized Inelastic Rods which are connected by hinges is another modeling option which is similar to the Lumped Masses Model, but neglects the elongation effect of the tether. It is described by Breukels (2011) and Williams (2006).

2.9 State Estimation Methods

The prediction of the current position of the kite is a challenging task because of the non-linear kite movements. The optimal solution requires a probability density function, which requires an infinite number of parameters (see Parzen (1962)). This chapter gives an overview over two suitable filters, which make presumptions to get to a finite number of parameters.

2.9.1 Kalman Filter

Kalman filter is the most widely used state estimator, which allows using a mathematical model to get meaningful data from error filled measurement data. Its estimation is based on the current state and a prediction about how controllable parts will change in the future. This includes making a comparison of the current measurement and the prediction, moderating the difference and adjusting the prediction that serves as new estimate. The more accurate the mathematical model is, the more exact the prediction will be. It uses the covariance and mean values for the prediction and is expensive but manageable in its computational time (Julier and Uhlmann (2004); Hjukse (2011)).

2.9.2 Double Exponential Smoothing-Based Prediction (DESP)

The Smoothing algorithm presented by LaViola (2003) runs approximately 135 times faster than Kalman and extended Kalman filter-based predictions in his test application. It delivers comparable results and has a much simpler implementation. It is a commonly used technique in economic and business forecasting, such as described by Box (1991). The advantage is that an estimator, which runs faster, doesn't have to predict as far in the future as a slower one. LaViola concluded that DESP is accurate, fast, robust and simple. This filtering method can also be used as a low pass filter that is also needed to process the angular sensor data. The following shows the DESP algorithm that is derived from Kalekar (2004), LaViola (2003), Box (1991) and Gardner (2006).

The Algorithm determines the actual measurement data prediction and its derivations recursively at a time step t . The measured data at a time t is x_t , its prediction is p_t and its derivation b_t . In economical papers refer to b_t as the trend, but the mathematical representation is the derivation of x_t over time. Furthermore α represents the weight on the current measurement x_t and β is the weight on the current derivation b_t .

For $t = 0$:

$$p_0 = \alpha x_1 \tag{2.4}$$

For $t = 1$:

$$p_1 = \alpha x_1 + (1 - \alpha) p_0 \tag{2.5}$$

$$b_1 = p_1 - p_0 \tag{2.6}$$

2 Fundamentals and Related Work

For $t > 1$:

$$p_t = \alpha x_t + (1 - \alpha)(p_{t-1} + b_{t-1}) \quad (2.7)$$

$$b_t = \beta(p_t - p_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta)b_{t-1} \quad (2.8)$$

If you use this prediction method for sensor fusion, the equations slightly change, because x_t is not longer a scalar, but a vector:

$$\vec{x}_t = (x_{t_1}, x_{t_2}, \dots, x_{t_n}) \quad (2.9)$$

The weights that are put on the sensors is also represented by a vectors $\vec{\alpha}$ and the weight on the derivate is β_t still scalar:

$$\vec{\alpha} = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n\}, \text{ where } \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \in [0, 1]. \quad (2.10)$$

The weights at time t is:

$$\vec{\alpha}_t = \{\alpha_{t_1}, \alpha_{t_2}, \dots, \alpha_{t_n}\}, \quad (2.11)$$

where

$$\forall i \in [1, \dots, n]. (\alpha_{t_i}, \beta_{t_i}) = \begin{cases} \alpha_i, \beta_i & , \text{ if } x_i \text{ is valid} \\ 0, 0 & , \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} . \quad (2.12)$$

The estimation combining the data of n sensors at a time t is p_t and the derivation is b_t . For $t = 0$, if $\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{0_i} > 0$:

$$p_0 = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{0_i}} \sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_{0_i} \cdot x_{0_i}). \quad (2.13)$$

For $t = 1$, if $\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{1_i} > 0$, otherwise start over:

$$p_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_{1_i} x_{1_i}) + \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{1_i}\right) p_0, \quad (2.14)$$

$$b_1 = p_1 - p_0. \quad (2.15)$$

For $t > 1$:

$$p_t = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{t_i} x_{t_i} + \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{t_i}\right) (p_{t-1} + b_{t-1}), \quad (2.16)$$

$$b_t = \beta_{t_i} (p_t - p_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta_{t_i}) (b_{t-1}). \quad (2.17)$$

The fusing mechanism puts a weight on each input data and calculates a position based

on the weights on the current data and the last estimate plus the derivative. This is a simple algorithm that is easy to implement. The tests in Chapter 6 will show if the result of this algorithm is sufficient.

2.10 Sensor Types for Angular Measurement

In this chapter the author describes the ad- and disadvantages of different sensor types for angular measurement. The general method to get the signal from movement is either optical, magnetically or mechanical using contacts. Potentiometers work with direct contact that modifies the resistance ratio depending on the position of the actuator. The advantage is that they are cheap and can be very accurate. The problems are their mechanical wear and their sensitiveness to vibration. Also an accurate potentiometer, which can rotate freely, could not be found. Incremental or absolute pulse encoders use contacts as well. Their digital output is mainly used to get the revolution speed. Another option is optical encoders, either with or without rotary encoder discs, which can be seen as a code wheel. The ones

Fig. 2.14: Encoder disc with 3-bit binary reflected gray code (Wikkrockiana (2004))

without rotary encoder discs can be found in every laser mouse. The reflection of a laser beam gives information about the movement of the surface that the laser points at. More accurate results can be obtained if a encoder disc is used. Most encoder discs use arrays of transparent and non-transparent lines. Fig. 2.14 shows a very simple encoder disc. A sensor which reads all three lines from the center to the outer part of the disc can determine in which eighth of the disc is at the moment. This gray code can also be used to determine the direction of a rotation. For example, if the sensor is at the top left eighth of the encoder disc (position : $[1,1,0]$) and reads $[0,1,0]$ in the next time step, it must be a clockwise rotation, whereas $[0,0,1]$ would be a counter clockwise rotation. These types are commonly used in printers. Magnetic encoders have encoder disc with different polarization. The Hall effect described by Hurd (1972) is used to determine the position of the actuator. Tab. 2.3 shows an overview about different sensor types.

2.11 Summary

Different AWE research groups face the same challenge: GNSS sensors can not guarantee reliable automatic control of kites. Measurements with the prototype of the TU Delft show this nicely. But there are several ways to compensate the GNSS inaccuracy during highly dynamic situations: Optical tracking, Galileo, differential GPS, orientation, tether length and angular sensors. Potentiometers, pulse-, optical- or magnetic-encoders can be used for angular measurement. Additionally, there are mainly two fusion algorithms presented in this chapter:

Method	Analog	Digital	Absolute	Incremental	Lifetime	Pro	Contra
potentiometric	x		x		10^8 cycles	high accuracy easy processing low cost	mechanical wear sensitive to vibration
pulse encoder		x	x	x	30000 cycles with speed of 600-1000 Hz	can rotate 360°+ low cost	low resolution
optical	x	x	x	x	long	very exact contact free almost wear-free	mechanical wear some need rotary disc, which is hard to mount and to adjust expensive sensitive to external disturbances (light)
magnetic	x	x	x	x	very long	exact durable contact free almost wear-free	expensive

Tab. 2.3: Sensor types (Hahn (2010); Ohtomo et al. (2000); Yamada et al. (1994); 7)

Kalman filter (widely used, complex, expensive) and DESP (fast, easy, similar results than Kalman). Fusing GNSS position with another position could improve the reliability of the kite position.

3 Approach

The recent chapters demonstrated motivation and research background for this thesis. It was found that positioning of the wing is a major challenge for AWE and that improvement is needed. One of the AWE concepts was explained in detail - the TU Delft prototype that already has two GNSS sensors for positioning. Other possible positioning methods were introduced because the GNSS sensors have drawbacks in highly dynamic situations. The author implements one alternative positioning method. It is mainly based on the length of the tether and the orientation of the tether. The previous chapter also described different algorithms to fuse this new position data with the existing GNSS positions. What will be described in this chapter?

On the one hand, the author explains the reference frames and derives an adopted version for this fusion algorithm. This is the basis for Chapter 5 - the design and implementation of the Software. On the other hand, he compares different sensor types and chooses the most suitable for the angular measurement, which is the groundwork for the design and implementation of the Hardware in Chapter 4.

3.1 Reference Frames

The EG reference frame is a right handed north, west, up frame with the origin at the tether exit point. That means, the zero position at the tether exit point at the ground station and the x-axis points to the geographical north, y to west and z points upwards. The coordinate systems, which are used in this thesis, are similar to the polar coordinate system of Beyer (1978) and Zwillinger (2011). They use ϕ for the vertical and θ for the horizontal angle. The starting point and direction of the angles in the coordinate system used in this thesis differ from the literature. The elevation ϕ is measured from the ground upwards and the azimuth angle θ starts at north (N) in positive clockwise direction. The kite distance r is equal to the radius r in the literature (see Fig. 3.1).

The Elevation-Azimuth-KiteDistance (EAK_{EG})

is described in Fig. 3.1 and Tab. 3.1.

	unit	range
ϕ	rad	$(-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]$
θ	rad	$(-\pi, \pi]$
r	m	\mathbb{R}^+

Tab. 3.1: EAK-EG

Fig. 3.1: Reference Frames

Elevation-Azimuth-Kite-Distance (ARC_{EG})

This reference frame is used to estimate the system state. Elevation and azimuth represent the arc length in meter. It is called the ARC coordinate system in EG reference frame and is described in Fig. 3.1 and Tab. 3.2.

	unit	range
$r\phi$	m	\mathbb{R}
$r\theta$	m	\mathbb{R}
r	m	\mathbb{R}

Tab. 3.2: ARC-EG

The geodetic coordinate system is used for GNSS coordinates. The definition and conversion to other reference frames is defined in Decker (1986).

3.2 Sensors

Tab. 3.3 gives an overview about requirements for the angular sensors. The sensors will be mounted at the tether exit point at the ground station. The elevation angle varies between approx. -40° to $+110^\circ$, so the sensor shall be able measure at least 180° . It is not necessary that this sensor rotates more than once, because of mechanical limitations. In contrary, the sensor for the azimuth angle shall be able to turn unlimited. According to an internal business

plan, the lifetime of the ground station is estimated with 20 years. Therefore, the sensors should last at least 20 years. Due to planned extensions of the ground station, the author shall use EtherCAT modules to connect the sensors to the processing machine. Another important aspect is the protection class of the sensors. The sensors shall bring protection innately, at least from dust and splashing water (IP64 defined by Commission et al. (2001)). It is simpler for the design of the mounting system, the post processing, the connection to the power supply and the digital hardware to use similar sensors for both measurements.

	Elevation	Azimuth
Range	180°	360°
Absolute accuracy	< 0.1°	< 0.1°
Multi turn	No	Yes
Protection	> IP64	> IP64
Lifetime	>= 20 Years	>= 20 Years
Connection	EtherCAT	EtherCAT

Tab. 3.3: Sensor Requirements

Tab. 3.4 shows suitable representatives of different sensor types. The specifications are taken from their data sheets¹²³⁴⁵. The main focus is on multi turn capability, the resolution and the IP rating. Which sensor should be used that fulfills the requirements?

The **optical encoders** in the table have no protection against water, light etc. and their resolution is maximum 1°. The only **potentiometer** with sufficient protection doesn't have multi turn and is not very accurate. The **absolute pulse encoder** could be used with a transmission of 30:1, but protection is also not sufficient. The best and most expensive encoder is an **absolute magnetic** encoder manufactured by Kuebler. Different versions are available with 12 Bit = $2^{12} = 4096$ pulses per turn (PPT), which is equivalent to a granularity of 0,088° for the azimuth and 0,044° for the elevation measurement. It has a IP67 protection, which means *“no ingress of dust [...] complete protection against contact [...] ingress of water in harmful quantity shall not be possible when the enclosure is immersed in water under defined conditions of pressure and time (up to 1 m of submersion)”*(see Commission et al. (2001)). The encoders are magnetic and measure almost wear-free (no contact between rotating and fixed part of sensor), which guarantees a very long lifetime. It can rotate infinitely while giving an absolute value of the position. The analog signal is also relatively easy to read and process with the EtherCAT module EL3068 (Data sheet can be found in the annex). Although this sensor is the most expensive one, it is the only one that meets the requirements. The Kübler sensors will be used for further developments.

¹<http://www.avagotech.com/docs/AV01-0215EN>

²<http://ie.farnell.com/avago-technologies/heds-9000-t00/encoder-rotary-2000ppr-2ch/dp/1654866?Ntt=HEDS-9000>

³<http://www.kuebler.com/english2/prod-sen-singleturn-3651.html>

⁴<http://www.conrad.de/ce/de/product/441545/TT-Electronics-AB-Cermet-Drehwiderstaende-IP67-Lin-22-k-1-W-20-/0241710&ref=list>

⁵<http://ie.farnell.com/bourns/eaw0j-b24-ae0128l/encoder-rotary/dp/9358234?Ntt=ace+128>

Name	Type	Resolution	IP	Output	Range	Prize [Euro]
Avago	reflective	212 LPI	none	digital	>360°	4,96
AEDR-8300-1Wx	optical					
Avago HEDS-9000	optical	360 LPI	none	digital	>360°	30,60
Kuebler Sendix 3651	absolute magnetic	12 Bit	IP67	analogue V	>360°	~150
TT Electronics C13	potentiometer	infinite	IP67	analogue V	250°	5,11
Bourns ACE 128	absolute pulse	128 PPT	IP40	digital	>360°	19,16

Tab. 3.4: Possible sensors

3.3 Kite State Estimation Method

The author describes in this section, which physical model he takes for the estimation, and how the general double exponential smoothing prediction algorithm (DESP) is adjusted to the kite power system. The DESP fusion algorithm was chosen because of several reasons. According to Uwe Fechner, the estimation error of a Kalman filter is unbounded. It minimizes the average error, not the maximal error, but for control purposes the maximal error must be bounded. Also, the Kalman filter assumes that the errors have a Gauss-distribution, which is not the case for the kite power application. The Kalman filter is computational expensive, which becomes relevant if the autopilot runs on the KCU in the future.

The accuracy of a Kalman filter depends on the accuracy of the model and even if the model is accurate and fast, the values for the Kalman filter have to be adjusted manually to every kite. DESP is an easy method to have a universal and fast prediction of the position. According to LaViola (2003), the DESP method delivers almost as valuable data like the Kalman filter. Also recent results of Fagiano et al. (2012) showed that the Kalman based filtering does not always deliver very good data. Another advantage is that the DESP prediction method can easily be improved by using the linear correlation between the steering input and the rate of turn as derived by Jehle (2012).

The Physical Model is the basis for the ARC-EG reference frame (see Fig. 3.1). The kite is forced to fly on a half sphere, which has a radius that is equal to the kite distance. DESP assumes that the velocity (in m/s) on the half sphere remains constant, as well as the reel-in/out speed, which is a valid assumption for short time predictions. That means that the prediction can be divided into three subcomponents:

1. the azimuth and the horizontal arc velocity of the kite on the sphere,
2. the elevation and the vertical arc velocity of the kite on the sphere,
3. the tether length and the tether reel-in/out speed.

It was also decided to take a rigid tether model for the angular position at first, in which the kite distance is equal to the tether length. The estimator can later be improved by adding a dynamic tether model.

The DESP Algorithm is adjusted for the TU Delft system. The measured positions at a time t is a vector of positions \vec{x}_t in ARC-EG (Section 3.1) coordinates. $p_t \in posARC_{EG}$ is the estimation of a time step t in the ARC-EG coordinate system. Three different positions are used for the estimation: The positions of Trimble, XSens (Tab. 2.2) and the angular position. The following definitions are used in the equations:

We substitute $Trimble = 0$, $XSens = 1$, and $Angular = 2$. Using the index for the sensor, we define the position array as

$$\vec{x}_t = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{x}_{t,Trimble} \\ \vec{x}_{t,XSens} \\ \vec{x}_{t,Angular} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{x}_{t,0} \\ \vec{x}_{t,1} \\ \vec{x}_{t,2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.1)$$

where positions of all sensors are in ARC-EG and include vertical arc length $r\theta$, horizontal arc length $r\phi$ and kite distance r in meter:

$$\vec{x}_{t,i} = \begin{pmatrix} r\phi_{t,i} \\ r\theta_{t,i} \\ r_{t,i} \end{pmatrix} \in posARC_{EG} \quad (3.2)$$

The Weights on the current measurement of the sensors \vec{x}_t and its derivative b_t is represented by $\vec{\alpha}_t$ and β with

$$\vec{\alpha}_t = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{t,0} \\ \alpha_{t,1} \\ \alpha_{t,2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.3)$$

where

$$\alpha_{t,i} = \begin{cases} \alpha_{t,i} & , \text{ if } x_{t,i} \text{ is valid and } \alpha_{t,i} > 0 \\ 0 & , \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}, \forall i \in [0, 1, 2] \quad (3.4)$$

and

$$\|\vec{\alpha}_t\| \in [0, 1].$$

Suggested values are:

$$\vec{\alpha}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{0,1} \\ \alpha_{0,2} \\ \alpha_{0,3} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 \\ 0.1 \\ 0.2 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\beta = 0.4.$$

The data of the first test showed that the angular sensors are more accurate the higher the force in the tether. So a linear weighting function was created to dynamically change the weights of the estimations during the flight, depending on the force at a time t in the tether F_t . This dynamic change is only applied if the estimator runs only with Trimble and angular positions. The calculation is depending on the force factor $f_t \in [0, 1]$:

$$f_t = \frac{\min(F_t, F_{max})}{F_{max}}, \text{ with } F_{max} = 3000 \quad (3.5)$$

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which is used for the new weight vector:

$$\vec{\alpha}_t = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{0,0} - \text{abs}(f_t \cdot \alpha_{0,2}) \\ \alpha_{0,1} \\ \alpha_{0,2} + \text{abs}(f_t \cdot \alpha_{0,0}) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.6)$$

The effect of this function is that the angular weight is at a minimum and the Trimble weight is at a maximum, when the force is low. The opposite is the case at maximum Force.

The Estimation is based on the calculated weight $\vec{\alpha}_t$, which is used to derive the weighted sum $\vec{\Sigma}x_t$ of the sensors for every time step. To get a valid azimuth velocity, even if the azimuth changes its sign, the azimuth has to be calculated with cosine, sinus and arctan2. Arctan2 is a variation of the tangent function, which returns the angle between the positive x-axis and a given 2D vector. It is defined as $(-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}] \times (-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}] \rightarrow (-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]$:

$$\text{arctan2}(x, y) = \begin{cases} \arctan(\frac{x}{y}) & x > 0 \\ \arctan(\frac{x}{y}) + \pi & y \geq 0, x < 0 \\ \arctan(\frac{x}{y}) - \pi & y < 0, x < 0 \\ +\frac{\pi}{2} & y > 0, x = 0 \\ -\frac{\pi}{2} & y < 0, x = 0 \\ \text{undefined} & y = 0, x = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

Let us define the weighted sum of all sensors as:

$$\vec{\Sigma}x_t = \begin{pmatrix} r\phi_t \\ r\theta_t \\ r_t \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.8)$$

where

$$r_t = \vec{\alpha}_t \cdot r_{t,i} \quad (3.9)$$

and

$$r\phi_t = \text{arctan2}(\phi_{t,\text{sin}}, \phi_{t,\text{cos}}) \cdot r_t, \quad (3.10)$$

$$r\theta_t = \text{arctan2}(\theta_{t,\text{sin}}, \theta_{t,\text{cos}}) \cdot r_t \quad (3.11)$$

where

$$\phi_{t,\text{sin}} = \sum_{i=0}^2 (\alpha_{t,i} \cdot \sin(\phi_{t,i})) \quad (3.12)$$

$$\phi_{t,\text{cos}} = \sum_{i=0}^2 (\alpha_{t,i} \cdot \cos(\phi_{t,i})) \quad (3.13)$$

$$\theta_{t,\text{sin}} = \sum_{i=0}^2 (\alpha_{t,i} \cdot \sin(\theta_{t,i})) \quad (3.14)$$

$$\theta_{t,cos} = \sum_{i=0}^2 (\alpha_{t,i} \cdot \cos(\theta_{t,i})) \quad (3.15)$$

The estimation at a time t can be found with the following algorithm:

For t=0, if $\|\vec{\alpha}_0\| > 0$:

$$p_0 = \frac{1}{\|\vec{\alpha}_0\|} \cdot \vec{\Sigma}x_t \quad (3.16)$$

For t=1, if $\|\vec{\alpha}_1\| > 0$, otherwise start over:

$$p_1 = \vec{\Sigma}x_t + (1 - \|\vec{\alpha}_1\|) \cdot p_0 \quad (3.17)$$

$$b_1 = \text{diff}(p_1, p_0) \quad (3.18)$$

For t>1:

$$p_t = \vec{\Sigma}x_t + (1 - \|\vec{\alpha}_t\|) \cdot (p_{t-1} + b_{t-1}) \quad (3.19)$$

$$b_t = \beta_t \cdot (\text{diff}(p_t, p_{t-1})) + (1 - \beta_t) \cdot (b_{t-1}), \quad (3.20)$$

where the difference of the positions is defined similar to the calculation of the weighted sum:

$$\text{diff}(p_1, p_2) : \text{posEAKD} \times \text{posEAKD} \longrightarrow \text{posEAKD}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{diff} \left(\begin{pmatrix} r\phi_{p_1} \\ r\theta_{p_1} \\ r_{p_1} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} r\phi_{p_2} \\ r\theta_{p_2} \\ r_{p_2} \end{pmatrix} \right) \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \arctan2((\sin(\phi_{p_1}) - \sin(\phi_{p_2})), (\cos(\phi_{p_1}) - \cos(\phi_{p_2}))) \cdot r_{p_1} \\ \arctan2((\sin(\theta_{p_1}) - \sin(\theta_{p_2})), (\cos(\theta_{p_1}) - \cos(\theta_{p_2}))) \cdot r_{p_1} \\ r_{p_1} - r_{p_2} \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (3.21)$$

3.4 Summary

Kübler sensors are taken for both angular measurements, the azimuth sensor has to measure 360° and the elevation sensor 180°. The estimation method calculates a prediction based on the current measurement \vec{x}_t and a estimated position which is the addition of the last prediction p_{t-1} and the kite 'velocity' b_{t-1} .

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4 Hardware Design and Implementation

The last chapter described which sensors are used for the angular measurements and the fusion algorithm. This chapter gives an overview about hardware design decisions and the author explains the mechanical and computer hardware choices. The next chapter will explain, how the DESP fusion algorithm is implemented.

4.1 Hardware Design

The mechanical hardware design is dependent on the construction of the current prototype. The tether starts from the drum, runs over three pulleys and exits at a movable part, which is called swivel. The swivel (see Fig. 4.1) can rotate freely. The author decided in coordination with Van Der Vlugt¹ that two separate constructions is the simplest way to mount both the elevation and the azimuth sensors.

A movable arm with a connection to the tether measures the elevation. The center of rotation is equal with the last pulley towards the kite. Fig. 4.2 shows that this is a valid approach, because the rotation of the arm in vertical direction is equal to the elevation ϕ if β is constant. Such a construction fulfills the requirements that are listed in Tab. 4.1. The elevation arm measures up to 180° . The fact that the kite can overfly the ground station on the one hand and cannot fly beneath the earth's surface on the other hand has to be taken into account. The starting point and the mechanical turning possibilities of the arm have to cope with these properties. The measurement range of the sensor shall be around -50° to 130° . Important is also that the elevation arm carries the wireless link antenna. This antenna is fundamental for the connection between the pod and the ground station and has to aim roughly towards the kite.

A modular concept is persecuted for the mechanical hardware design to guaranty maximum flexibility. Certain parts of the construction can be replaced or optimized and additional parts, such as a camera mount, can be added. This flexibility includes the possibility to attach other types of angular sensors as well. For a long lifetime, the construction shall have low friction, be stainless and solid. A transmission is not needed. Most of the requirements (see Tab. 4.1) are also transferable to the azimuth mounting construction (see Tab. 4.2). The big difference is that this construction has to be able to rotate freely; therefore sliding contacts for the signal of the elevation sensor and the wireless antenna are desirable.

To transmit and digitalize the sensor data, the sensors are connected to the EL3068 EtherCAT terminal, which will be explained in the following paragraph.

EtherCAT is a fast, flexible field bus system. Fig. 4.3 shows how terminals can be connected through a coupler to a computer or embedded system. The terminals can be used for many types of analogue or digital inputs. The main advantage of field bus systems such as EtherCAT is that only one wire is required to connect all I/O devices to the controlling

¹Van Der Vlugt is the head for mechanical engineering of the TU Delft research group

Fig. 4.1: The swivel

Requirement		Note
Rotation range	180°	elevation is limited
Wireless link mountable	yes	connection to KCU
Modular	yes	broken parts can be replaced
Other sensors mountable	yes	flexibility
Low friction	yes	precision, low hysteresis, lifetime
Stainless	yes	lifetime
Transmission	no	not needed
Durable/ Solid	yes	20 year lifetime
Camera mountable	optional	video analysis/ optical tracking

Tab. 4.1: Elevation arm requirements

What		Why
Rotation range	>360°	swivel rotates freely
Modular	yes	broken parts can be replaced
Other sensors mountable	yes	flexibility
Low friction	yes	precision, low hysteresis, lifetime
Stainless	yes	lifetime
Transmission	no	not needed
Durable/ Solid	yes	20 year lifetime
Sliding contacts	optional	unlimited rotations of swivel possible

Tab. 4.2: Azimuth requirements

Fig. 4.2: Elevation arm theory

Fig. 4.3: EtherCAT environment (Burgers (2010))

computer. Only one driver for the field bus protocol is needed for the communication between host and terminals. The main drawback of field buses is that they have more latency and/or jitter compared to data acquisition cards. Beckhoff (2013) claims that they reduced the latency of their EtherCAT systems to less than $30 \mu s$ for 1000 I/O devices.

4.2 Hardware Implementation

The elevation arm is designed to be modular and flexible. All parts are attached to the two main pieces on both sides of the swivel (Fig. 4.4; 4). The main parts are two aluminum wheels with 30mm radius, running on closed ABEC 5 skateboard bearings on a 8mm axel. Stainless steel bars with a 8mm diameter are connected to this construction (Fig. 4.4; 2). Additional components can be mounted to these wheels, but the current setup includes:

Firstly, an U-shaped bar that has a mount for the wireless antenna (Fig. 4.4; 3).

Secondly, a counterweight construction (Fig. 4.4; 5, 6): The distance of the counterweight can be adjusted to keep the construction in balance at an elevation angle of 20° . This allows putting more weight on the construction while still keeping the arm balanced so that the arm can follow the tether at a minimal force.

Thirdly, the connection to the tether: The arm is connected to the tether with two pulleys

Fig. 4.4: Elevation arm. Views from top left to bottom down: front left, front right, left, right.

with closed bearings (Fig. 4.4; 1). They are suitable for a tether diameter up to 6mm.

The most important part is still the sensor mount (Fig. 4.4; 7, 8). The Kübler Sendix 3651 is mounted on a base plate, which is connected to the solid part of the swivel. Its axis is connected with an adapter to the right aluminum wheel. Three screws hold the axel in position and turns of the elevation arm are transferred 1:1 to the sensor. It is possible to mount other sensors but it might be necessary to bend a new base plate, and to grind a new adaptor. This construction fulfills all requirements that are listed in Tab. 4.3.

The Azimuth sensor is mounted on a base plate beneath the swivel mounting plate. It is connected to the swivel through three gear wheels. The diameter of the gear wheel, which is connected to the sensor, is equal to the gear wheel at the swivel, so the transition is 1:1. Because the gear wheels are made of plastic, they are sensible to mechanical impacts. Therefore, a temporarily aluminum cover was constructed for a basic protection. This construction is not modular: the gear wheels can not be replaced the construction can not be extended. Nevertheless, different sensor types can be mounted, needing another adaptor when the axle is bigger than 6mm. The materials used for this construction are not prone to rust, sun or rain. For an overview see Tab. 4.4.

Requirement		Result	
Rotation range	180°	✓	250°
Wireless link mountable	yes	✓	
Modular	yes	✓	
Other sensors mountable	yes	✓	maximum axle diameter 11mm
Low friction	yes	✓	abec 5 bearings
Stainless	yes	✓	aluminum & stainless steel
Transmission	no	✓	
Durable/ Solid	yes	✓/✓	
Camera mountable	optional	✓	

Tab. 4.3: Elevation arm results

Requirement		Result	
Rotation range	>360°	✓	
Modular	yes	x	special printer parts used, not easy to replace
Other sensors mountable	yes	✓	adapter needed
Low friction	yes	✓	journal bearing
Stainless	yes	✓	aluminum, stainless steel & plastic
Transmission	no	✓	
Durable/ Solid	yes	✓/x	cable to swivel can have corrupting influence
Sliding contacts	optional	x	

Tab. 4.4: Azimuth results

The EtherCAT module is located in the electrical cabinet of the winch. It is connected to a link box through an HR30 connector. It is a waterproof (IP67) connector, which is also used for the connection between link box and sensors. The connectors also serve as weak link for the elevation sensor. The swivel can possibly rotate more than 5 times, which causes the weak link to break, cutting the connection between elevation sensor and EtherCAT module. The connection can be regained by plugging the cable back in. The EtherCAT module, as well as the sensors, are connected to the 24V power supply of the winch. The EtherCAT module is connected to the controller through a RJ45 Ethernet cable. The wire diagram is shown in Fig. 4.5.

4.3 Summary

The elevation arm is a solid, modular construction and the azimuth sensor can rotate freely. The mounting constructions for both sensors can also cope with different sensor types. The sensors are connected with a weak link to a fuse box, which sends the data to the controlling computer via EtherCAT.

Fig. 4.5: Wire Diagram

5 Software Design and Implementation

The last chapters showed why an alternative position is useful and how angular sensors were attached to the TU Delft prototype. This chapter describes the software part. It includes the graphical user interface (GUI) and the underlying processing and fusion algorithms. However, the kite power team of the TU Delft already has a complex software structure and use different frameworks. Especially for the sensor fusion, the software design has to adapt to the given structure.

5.1 Design

The general message delivery protocol is a Google Protocol Buffer (Protobuf) container, defined by Google (2013) that is send over an ZeroMQ link as described by iMatrix (2013). This ensures hardware, programming language and platform independent inter process communication and data logging over Ethernet with varying message lengths. All software components are supervised by one main program, the system state monitor. So before going too much into detail, it is necessary to define the changes for an operator supervising the system. If angular sensors are added to the system and a new system state estimation is implemented, there are three new use-cases for the operator (Fig. 5.1).

1. The operator shall be able to switch the type of estimation. It must be possible to select any set of sensors as estimation input.
2. In case that the operator wants to use an estimation that uses angular sensors, he must be able to calibrate the sensors by changing the offsets. This includes that the offsets of the sensors are displayed.
3. The operator shall be able to display or suppress WinchState messages containing the EtherCAT data.

However, to fulfill these requirements, let us see what has to happen in the backend. First, the angular position has to be transferred to the kite state estimator. EtherCAT is a very fast for a field bus system. EtherCAT allows an easy and unique connection of many different I/O modules to the host machine. It is easy to add terminals to the module stack and to process the data once it has been set up. It was decided that the Orocos (2013) framework is used for sensor data post processing. Orocos is a control framework used in robotics and automation, which includes drivers for EtherCAT terminals and allows hard real time processing.

Orocos

The TU Leuven and other control research groups have used Orocos for more than 10 years. An Orocos program includes a set of components. Each component represents one task and runs in a separate thread at a defined period. The big advantage is that components can be

Fig. 5.1: Use cases

started, stopped and linked to other components dynamically during runtime. The components communicate through thread safe ports and can offer or access services.

In this project, three Orocos components were used: The EtherCAT driver offers a service to access sensor data from the terminals. The Filter component accesses the service and reads the data at 200Hz, offering filtered data at its output port or as a service. Another component, the Publisher, shall be triggered by a clock, read the data from the Filter and publish the data with ZeroMQ, thus making it accessible for other programs. The decision whether to use a port or a service for the connection between Filter and Publisher depends on many factors. A service can be called independently and can be executed by the calling or owning thread. A port can produce message overhead but on the other hand many components can listen to one port. Fig. 5.2a shows an overview over both solutions. EventMsg and WinchState are ZeroMQ Protobuf messages that are received/ send over the network. The Publisher can access the sensor data through the dataPort or the FilteredData service. The Filter component calls the Slave_1004 service of the Maser component to get the sensor data. The Slave_1004 service uses the driver for the EtherCAT EL 3068 terminal and reads the analogue input. The read function returns the last read value of a channel. Fig. 5.2c and Fig. 5.2b shows the workflow of filtering and publishing the WinchState. On the one side, the Filter connects to the service Slave_1004 before it can read, filter and write the sensor data to the dataPort at 200Hz. Additionally, the angular velocity is calculated in the Filter component, because it has much lower delay compared to the 20Hz frequency of the Publisher. On the other side, the Publisher reads the filtered data from the port whenever it is triggered by a clock event, and publishes a WinchState message. The communication through the port is handled by the Orocos core, which runs in the background.

The Angular Position is calculated based on the Rigid Tether Model (see Section 2.8). The tether is assumed to be straight, which is a valid assumption if there is high force on the tether. The dynamic weighting of the estimation algorithm takes this effect into account.

The System State Estimation algorithm has been described in Section 3.3. For the design of the software it is important to include it in the existing software structure at a position, where it can get all the relevant data, and where the data can be accessed whenever it is necessary. A system state estimator program (SystemStateEstimator) is already implemented. The SystemStateEstimator has a central position in the software architecture. It receives sensor data from the KCU, the ground station and the wind sensors, processes them and publishes messages that contain the current system state (SystemStateEstimation message). This includes $v_{w,g}$, $F_{t,g}$, position and more. It is basically all information the the autopilot (Autopilot_2LAP), the central control (CentralControl), the flight path controller (FlightPathController) and the graphical user interface (GUI) need (see Fig. 5.3). There is a simple estimation that repeats the old position of the kite in case that there is no valid position available. Therefore, this is the best place to put the new system state estimator. Figure Fig. 5.3 shows the relevant part of the systems class diagram. The new class is called KitePosEstimator and receives the position data (XSens, Trimble and angular) from its owning instance of the class SystemStateEstimator as shown in Fig. 5.4. To make a correct estimation, the KitePosEstimator needs to get a valid ground position. The estimation shall be read after a new estimate is calculated. The current angular position is also published in the EstimatesSystemState message. Optionally, calling onNewSensors changes the sensors that are used for the estimate.

5.2 Software Implementation

The last section gave an overview about the design of the software. This section describes how and where the software is implemented.

5.3 Environment

The following operating system and software is used for the implementation. All software is written in C++.

- Ubuntu 12.04 - Linux distribution.
- QtCreator 2.4.1 based on Qt 4.8.1
- ZeroMQ-3.2.2 (recommended, also compatible with 2.1.11 and lower)
- Google Protocol Buffers 2.4.1
- Orocos Toolkit 2.6.0
- Ros Fuerte Desktop

(a) Orocos components diagram

(b) Filter Sensor Data

(c) Publish WinchState

Fig. 5.2: Sequential diagrams

Fig. 5.3: Software structure by Fechner

Fig. 5.4: Sequence diagram of state estimation

- Soem EtherCAT drivers 2.5

Developing System:

- MacBook Pro late 2008

Executing Systems:

- Pipal industrial PC
- Taskrunner embedded system

5.4 Implementation Aspects

For the Orocos Component Structure, two different implementations are possible. The author implemented both versions and performed speed tests.

Firstly, the Publisher accesses the data from the Filter using a service of the Filter. Tab. 5.1 shows the time delays between the software components according to the sequence diagram of Fig. 5.2c. The Publisher component is running on Taskrunner. The clock server that sends the clock events and the Protologger program, which logs the WinchState messages, are running on Pipal. The time delays are measured under perfect conditions and under load. The network traffic, which was recorded on the 25th of October (a real test flight), simulates load in the network. Following times were measured:

- The time between sending the clock event from Pipal,
- receiving the event by the Publisher on Taskrunner,
- sending the WinchState message by the Publisher,
- receiving the WinchState message by the Protologger back on Pipal.

The average and maximum value during a simulation time of 5 min was measured. Tab. 5.1 shows that the time that a ZeroMQ message needs to be send over the network is 0,5 ms to 0,8 ms in average. The average round trip time is 1,6 ms. Load slows the message delivery down but has no influence on the processing time. The processing time, the time between a clock event was received and the WinchState was send, is 0,5 ms in average and 0,7 ms max. A 24-hour test took 0,8 ms avg. and 7,5 ms max for the processing. These time delays are high and show that the Orocos core cannot process service calls very fast if the component, which owns the service, is busy.

Secondly, the Filter and the Publisher use a port for the communication instead of a service. The results of the speed test were much better: An average processing time of 0.022 ms and a maximum of 0.096 is more than 10 times faster than the service implementation. Therefore it was concluded that ports should be used for the final implementation.

The System State Estimator is implemented as described in Chapter 4 and Section 3.3.

		Pub rec.		Pub send		Protolog rec.	
		load		load		load	
Clock send	avg.	0,5	0,6	0,9	1,1	1,6	1,6
	max	0,9	0,8	1,5	1,9	2,2	6,0
Pub rec.	avg.			0,5	0,5	0,9	0,9
	max			0,7	0,7	1,1	3,8
Pub send	avg.					0,8	0,8
	max					1,0	1,1

Tab. 5.1: TimeDelays in ms for the service setup. Testing period = 5min

5.5 Project Structure

The design chapter described the general structure of the software and this section goes into more detail by showing the class diagrams of the Orocos and the SystemStateEstimator parts. Finally an extension of Fig. 5.3 is presented. Because of simplicity, only major changes and the public functions are displayed in the Figures.

The SystemStateEstimator Class Diagram is shown in Fig. 5.5. New type definitions have been added, which represent the reference frames that are explained in Section 3.1. The KitePosEstimator uses these data structures to save the last received positions and the last estimated position. It is the main new class, which is owned by the SystemStateEstimator. The data flow of the functions is described in the sequential diagram of Fig. 5.4.

The Orocos Component Diagram can be seen in Fig. 5.6. The three major components `~~ Publisher, Filter, SoemMaster ~~` are shown. An RTT Port must be used for the communication between Publisher and Filter. RTT is a library used by Orocos for inter-thread communication. A framework program `~~ the deployer ~~` starts all components and connects their ports using a custom startup script. This script can be written in the Orocos syntax or in XML. Each input port of a component can only be connected to exactly one output port, but other input ports can also be connected to the same output port. Thus, a one-to-many connection for a component point of view is possible. The connection between the Filter and the SoemDriver, which is a service owned by the SoemMasterComponent has been described in the previous section. A new class is the `DESP_Filter`, which serves as a low pass filter. Every time, when the Filter reads a new value from the sensors, it passes them to the `DESP_Filter` by calling the `setNewValue(...)` that returns smoothed sensor data and the angular velocity. The `DESP_Filter` can run at any constant frequency. In the future it is possible to use this filter as a predictor to compensate tether delays.

The Software Structure which was introduced in Fig. 5.3 is the basis for Fig. 5.7. A minor difference is, that some GUI components run on Pipal instead of on the kite control laptop. The overview points out, that the Publisher, which is running on Taskrunner, sends the ZeroMQ WinchState message (which is described as `<< flowport >>`) to the SystemStateEstimator. Every new position is sent the KitePosEstimator daemon at arrival. The

Fig. 5.5: SystemStateEstimator class diagram

Fig. 5.6: Orocos class diagram

Fig. 5.7: Extended software structure

KitePosEstimator calculates a new estimate, when is triggered by the SystemStateEstimator (at 20Hz). The position estimation is included in the EstimatedSystemState message, which is published in the LAN.

The documentation can be found on the Kitepower.eu wiki or in the code.

5.6 Graphical User Interface (GUI)

The user that operates the system can control the estimation with the GUI. Possible interaction between the operator and the system were displayed in Fig. 5.1. The use-cases are implemented in different GUI elements. The core functionality of the estimation is added to the CentralControl (Fig. 5.8b). The view of the measured angles and the offsets are displayed in the DataDisplay (Fig. 5.8a) and the ProtoLogger (Fig. 5.8c) shows the processing time of the sensor data on the OrocOS side. An operator can change to the desired estimation method with three checkboxes in the CentralControl. Having none of the boxes checked will result in using the old estimation. As soon as one or more checkboxes are active, the DESP estimation is active and uses the data of the sensors that are checked. The TrimbleAtSwivel checkbox can be used to acquire Trimble to measure the position of the ground station. The Trimble has to be at the ground station for this calibration. The DataDisplay shows the elevation and azimuth angles calculated from the GNSS data and the angular sensor data in degrees. Also the offset between those values is displayed. This offset has to be added to the Publisher configuration file before an estimation, which based on the angular sensors, can be made. The last GUI component, that was changed, is the Protologger. It is designed to log and display all messages in the network. It can be selected, which messages shall be displayed. Additionally it displays the average and maximum processing time of the sensor

(a) DataDisplay

(b) CentralControl

(c) ProtoLogger

Fig. 5.8: GUI components

data in Orocos (see Section 5.4).

5.7 Further Developments and possible Extensions

The Angular Sensor data could also be send from the Master component to the Filter component through a port. This could lead to a speed-up of the processing time as regarded in the speed tests of the communication between Publisher and Filter (Section 5.4). But the difference here is, that the Master component runs in idle mode until it gets a service call from the Filter. Using ports would include running the Master and the Filter component at 200Hz, which increases the CPU load and could also slow down the whole workflow. Also an automatic calibration could be added, that sets the offset between angular sensor position and GPS position. Until now, this has to be performed manually by looking on the DataDisplay and writing the offset in the settings file of the Publisher.

The Angular Position could be optimized by implementing a realistic tether model. Then the angular position could also be used in situations of low force in the tether. Interesting pre investigations can be found in the test results section. A combination of these results with the lumped mass model could increase the accuracy of the angular position significantly.

The Estimation of the kite position could be extended by additional position information. In most cases, the more position information is added, the better the result. Making a dependency between the current heading and the steering input could optimize the estimation itself. Jehle (2012) describes a correlation between the steering input and the rate of turn. To do so, the parameters of this correlation have to be adjusted to the new kite. But having such additional information would make the estimation more precise and more stable in case of GNSS failures.

5.8 Summary

The fusion algorithm is included in the given software structure. An Operator can control its behavior with the CentralControl and can supervise the calibration and the data flow with the ProtoLogger and the DataDisplay.

6 Test Results

The recent chapter explained the hardware and software implementation of the angular sensors and the system state estimation. The following chapter is divided into three parts. Firstly, the behavior and the test results of the angular sensors from the 25th of October 2012 are presented. The correlation of the tether sag and the aerodynamic forces are examined, which gives an indication about the grade of influence of the aerodynamic forces. The second part describes the lab tests that were performed to test the system state estimator in different flight conditions. The results of this simulation are compared to the behavior of the estimation and the autopilot under real conditions. The third part includes test results of the estimation with real test data. The Rooted Mean Square Error (RMSE) gives an indication about the accuracy of the estimation. The RMSE is the average difference between a given data and a reference data.

6.1 Theoretical Results and Test Design

theoretical results are the results that can be expected by looking at physical properties of the tether in the kite power system.

Fig. 6.1: Expectations during figure of 8

The Tether Fig. 6.1 was created according to observations during the test and a the video analysis of test flights. The tether has a diameter of 4mm, a weight of $9,1 \cdot 10^{-3} \frac{kg}{m}$ and a maximum length of 1000m (see Chapter 2). The whole tether has a weight of 9,1 kg, which is certainly not much, but a maximum gravity force of $G = m \cdot g = 9,1kg \cdot 9,81 \frac{N}{kg} = 89,271N$ pulls the tether towards the ground as shown in Fig. 2.13. According to Eq. 2.3, the horizontal displacement is proportional to the drag force, which is proportional to A and the square

of $v_{a,t}$. The vertical displacement is also proportional to drag force and gravity, thus also to A and $v_{a,t}$. Fig. 6.1 takes this effects into account and shows the difference of two kite positions. The blue position is based on the angular measurement assuming a straight. The red one is the real kite position during a figure of eight movement. The figure of eight is designed such that the kite makes down turns at the corners and performs a diagonal upwards movement during crosswind flight in the center of the eight. During the down turns, there is low horizontal velocity, and the gravity and drag force in are counteracting each other in vertical direction. Therefore the angular measurement should be the best during the turns at the outer part of the eight. In diagonal crosswind flight, the horizontal velocity is at a maximum while the gravity force and the drag force have the same direction. The angular measurement should differ the most during this crosswind motion.

The Kite State Estimator has to cope with following situations:

- The loss of data from one, two or all sensors for a limited time. In this case, the estimator shall give out reasonable position estimations until going back to ideal mode. If all sensor signals are lost, the estimator shall simulate the kite flying at a constant tether reel out speed v_t and constant speed on the half sphere.
- A GNSS error during highly dynamic situations. The estimator shall limit the influence of these wrong positions by changing the weights of the sensors dynamically.

6.2 Angular Sensor Test on 2012/10/25

This section analyzes the first data from the angular sensors that was obtained during the flight test at Valkeburg on the 25th of October in 2013. The angular data is compared to the angles, which are calculated from the Trimble GNSS. All angles have been transformed into the downwind reference frame, which is similar to the EG reference frame, with the difference that the x-axis points downwind. The angles are converted to degrees and the elevation and the azimuth measurement are regarded separately.

6.2.1 Azimuth Angle

The range of the measured data is from zero to ten Volts, which represent degrees from -179 to 180, a.k.a. $(-pi, pi]$ in EAK_{EG} reference frame. The measurement is linear, which means it can be converted into degrees directly by multiplying with 36. The down wind direction has to be taken into account to compare it with the GNSS azimuth direction in the wind reference frame. The average downwind direction (which is changing) and the GNSS azimuth are subtracted from the measured angle in degree. An average of the resulting values over one pumping cycle (from 4580-4900 s relative time) is taken as an offset for the measured data. Fig. 6.2 shows the corrected measured sensor Azimuth and the GNSS-Azimuth, as well as the tether force.

Fig. 6.2: Azimuth angles during two pumping cycles containing three figure of eight each. The two curves fit better on high force.

The first impression leads to the presumption that the measured data fits very well when there is high force in the tether (4600-4700 s), whereas there is a bigger difference during low force phases (4700-4750 s). The quantitative difference of the GNSS and the measured angles against the force is shown in Fig. 6.3. The rooted mean square errors proof the assumption that the angular measurement is more accurate during high force phases: it is 1.08° during high force and 2.54° during low force. The accuracy of the measured azimuth is higher if the force is higher.

Fig. 6.3: Error and force

The correlation between force and error that was assumed in the previous sections is also found in the measurement data. The measured value differs from the estimation depending on the orientation of the kite. The angles are almost the same during turns whereas the angles differ much during crosswind flight (see Fig. 6.4). That means the faster the change of the azimuth angle, the bigger the difference. A correlation between the measured azimuth angle and its derivation, which is proportional to the speed of the tether in horizontal direction, can be found in the measurement data. Fig. 6.5 shows that the derivative of the azimuth is almost proportional to the difference: rising and falling edges as well as minima, maxima and zero points are at the same position.

Fig. 6.4: Difference between measured and GNSS azimuth

Fig. 6.5: Correlation between the derivation of the GNSS azimuth and the difference of measured and GNSS azimuth angle during a figure of eight: The curves are similar.

Fig. 6.6 shows the result of shifting the measured data by -200 ms. The two angles fit almost perfectly and the mean square error during a pumping cycle drops down to 0.58° . This means that a prediction algorithm could improve the accuracy of the ground measurements significantly.

Fig. 6.6: Azimuth comparison after shifting the measured curve by -200ms

Finally, the correlation between the RMSE and the tether length was examined. Surprisingly the change of the tether length has low influence on the accuracy of the measured angle, although the gravity and the drag force is proportional the area A of the tether. No pumping cycle, which was performed during the test flight on the 25th of October, showed a significant correlation that would allow a valid statement. A representative figure of eight plot can be seen in Fig. 6.7.

Fig. 6.7: No obvious correlation between the tether length and the difference between measured and GNSS azimuth

6.2.2 Elevation Angle

The elevation sensor has the same range as the azimuth sensor (0-10 V) but measures only an angle form -89° to 90° . This means it is supposed to be twice as accurate. The offset for the measured angle is calculated by taking the average difference of estimation and measurement over the whole test day. It is remarkable that the lowest corrected measured angle in Fig. 6.8 is higher than the GNSS one (4600-4700 s). This is possible in situations, where the drag force is higher than the gravity force. Another reason could be that the calculated offset is too high.

According to theory and the test data, the difference of the angles is proportional to the tether force: the lower the force, the higher the difference and vice versa. This can be seen in Fig. 6.9.

The derivative of the estimation can be taken as an indicator for the error between the angles, although the correlation is not that direct (see Fig. 6.10). Shifting the measurement data by 200ms could reduce the error (see Fig. 6.11).

For the first cycle of the third autopilot period on the 25th, starting at a relative time of 4580 s, the mean square error dropped from 1.02° to 0.8° during high force flight. The graphical representation of the first figure of 8 is shown in Fig. 6.11. As for the azimuth angle there seems to be little influence of the tether length to the error. In Fig. 6.12, the error rises at the end of the last figure of eight (4700 s and 4870 s) but this is related to a strong drop of the force at the same time.

Another challenge to be aware of is a vibration of the tether that creates a loud noise during operation. Sinusoidal oscillation of the tether in vertical direction was recorded but it is not clear whether it represents the tether vibration. Oscillation in horizontal direction could not be found in the measurement data.

Fig. 6.8: Azimuth angles during two pumping cycles containing three figures of eight each. The two curves fit better at high force

Fig. 6.9: Correlation of force and error

6.2.3 Conclusion

The data from the angular sensors match with the position obtained from the GNSS sensor. This is especially true if simple corrections are applied, namely a time shift of 200 ms. Fig. 6.13 shows a figure of eight based on the measurement and the estimation. The amplitude of the azimuth is the same; only the amplitude of the measured elevation is lower. The forces on the tether and the speed of the tether have a big influence on the difference between measured and calculated angles, whereas a 400m reel out of the tether has no noticeable effect.

Fig. 6.14 shows the rooted mean square error (RMSE) of the azimuth during two high force phases, one low force phase and the average. The RMSE of the azimuth is from 1.0° to 1.1° during high force, 2.5° during the low force phase and around 1.4° in average. Taking a time delay of 200ms into account, the RMSE average drops below 0.9° . This would be a difference of 15m on a maximum tether length of 1000m. The elevation angle gives similar results. The RMSE during the first figure of eight drops from 1° to 0.8° when taking a delay of 200ms into account.

Nevertheless, even a 1.0° error is still high and it has to be further investigated and tested whether the angular measurement is sufficient for calculating the position as a basis for the autopilot. It is also possible to make an empiric correlation between the error and the square

Fig. 6.10: Correlation of error and slope of the GNSS elevation angle

Fig. 6.11: The two angles after shifting the measurement data by 200ms

of the angular velocity. The theory shows that this is a valid approach. According to Eq. 2.3, D is proportional to the square of the tether velocity v_t , which is proportional to the angular velocity θ^* by definition. Assuming, that the air pressure ρ_{air} and the aerodynamic properties of the tether c_D are constant. Further, the area A , which is proportional to the tether length, has a negligible effect on the difference of the angles as shown by the measurement data. Also, the elevation difference is constant on low force, as shown in Fig. 6.9. With these simplifications, following correlation can be defined:

$$\theta = \begin{cases} \theta^* - c_\theta \cdot \dot{\theta}^{*2} & , \dot{\theta}^* \geq 0 \\ \theta^* + c_\theta \cdot \dot{\theta}^{*2} & , \dot{\theta}^* < 0 \end{cases} \quad (6.1)$$

$$\phi = \begin{cases} \phi^* - c_\phi \cdot \dot{\phi}^{*2} & , \dot{\phi}^* \geq 0 \\ \phi^* + c_\phi \cdot \dot{\phi}^{*2} & , \dot{\phi}^* < 0 \end{cases} \quad (6.2)$$

Where c_ϕ and c_θ are constant factors derived from the measurement data. As an illustration, $c_\theta = 0.333$ was derived from the measurement data and Fig. 6.14 also shows the RMSE taking these corrections into account, with a significant result: the average RMSE drops to 0.75° . This correction includes no time shifting, but shows better results for the sample data. It has to be remembered, that this is just one example and can not be taken as a general correction method, before it is further validated. For the first version of the Kite

Fig. 6.12: No obvious correlation between tether length and error

Fig. 6.13: Figure of eight based on measured and GNSS angles

State Estimator, the raw position data is taken without any correction.

6.3 Kite State Estimator Test Simulation

The test of the angular sensors showed that the data is generally usable to determine an alternative position. This section looks at the fusing algorithm. The `SystemStateEstimator` and the `KitePosEstimator` were tested using simulated kites. The tests are implemented in Python. A kite class represents a kite, which is flying on a defined trajectory. The speed of the kite and the reel out speed of the tether can be chosen. The main program sets up the `SystemStateEstimator` and sends simulated sensor data to the estimator. It receives the estimated position and plots it into a 3D diagram. Fig. 6.15 shows the basic data flow between the `SystemStateEstimator`, the Python main test class and the kite position class. ZeroMQ and Google Protobuf ensure the communication between estimator and the main class. An instance of the kite position class represents the position of a kite that is updated once every time step. **Three instances of the kite** were created: the **Trimble** position, the **XSens** position and the **ideal** position. The angular position and the dynamic force weighting are not simulated.

The kite positions can be suppressed for a defined time and noise or errors can optionally be added. Noise added to (ϕ, θ, r) in the EAK-EG reference frame. Gaussian noise can be

Fig. 6.14: Square errors of the third autopilot period on 25.10.2012

Fig. 6.15: Sequential diagram of Python test environment

added to the kite positions. Additionally, errors with a defined frequency can be added to the position data (horizontal = 40 m and vertical = 30 m for Trimble (-20 m for Xsens)). It is also possible to suppress the Trimble data at a defined frequency to simulate packet losses. In Tab. 6.3, the noise is denoted as percentage of noise plus error frequency. An error frequency of -1 defines that the position at the beginning is $(0, 0, 0)^T \in posARC - EG$. Negative error frequencies create packet losses by suppressing the Trimble signal (e.g. -4 suppresses the Trimble signal every 4th time step). The kite flies different figures, which are listed in Tab. 6.1.

Fig.	Meaning	Ideal trajectory
	vertical circle in the north/up plane	ϕ from 0 to $\frac{\pi}{2}$, $\theta = 0$, $kd = 100$
—	horizontal circle in the north/west plane	$\phi = 0$, θ from $-\pi$ to π , $kd = 100$
○	circle	$\phi_{\varnothing} = 0$, $349 \approx 20^\circ$ $\Delta\theta = 0$, $349 \approx 20^\circ$
∞	figure of eight	$\phi_{\varnothing} = 0$, $349 \approx 20^\circ$ $\Delta\theta = 0$, $349 \approx 20^\circ$

Tab. 6.1: Flight maneuvers

A half circle is denoted as $0,5 \cdot \bigcirc$ in Tab. 6.3. To simulate real conditions, the kite flies at a constant offset to the ideal trajectory. It is highly probable, that the real position is somewhere in between the GNSS sensor positions of Trimble and XSens. The real positions of the kite are represented by the ideal positions with a tether length of 100m and an elevation angle of 20° . Trimble positions are slightly west and higher than the ideal positions. XSens positions are lower and east of the ideal positions. To make a scientifically valid statement about the performance of the estimator, the RMSE between the three trajectories and the ideal trajectory is calculated and listed in Tab. 6.3 and Tab. 6.4. The Figure also gives an overview about 21 tests that were performed. The naming convention of positions and the resulting trajectories of the sensors, the estimation and the ideal kite is listed in 6.2.

	Position	Trajectory	Note
Trimble	X-Pos	X-Traj	Result of the Estimation The ideal position and trajectory simulates the real kite.
XSens	T-Pos	T-Traj	
Estimated	E-Pos	E-Traj	
Ideal	I-Pos	I-Traj	

Tab. 6.2: Notation

6.3.1 Simulation with one kite

For the simulation, one kite position per time step is sent as T-Pos. The weights for the estimation are:

$$\vec{\alpha}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{0,Trimble} \\ \alpha_{0,XSens} \\ \alpha_{0,Angular} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 \\ 0.0 \\ 0.0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\beta = 0.4$$

This means a 1:1 ratio of the last E-Pos and the new T-Pos. If not defined differently, the starting tether length r_0 is 100m. The detailed results can be found in Tab. 6.3¹.

¹How to read Tab. 6.3: Test no. 3 performs 50% of a circle that takes 30s with a reel out speed of 0 m/s. The estimated position has a RMSE for the elevation of 1.99 m, for the azimuth 0.99 m, for the kite distance 0,17 and a mean RMSE of 1.05 m. The Trimble position has noise of 0.0 percent and an error frequency of 0.

6.3 Kite State Estimator Test Simulation

#	Fig.	t [s]	v_t [$\frac{m}{s}$]	Position	inactive from [$\frac{\% \text{ cycle time}}{100}$]	for [s]	Noise	RMSE [m]			
								$r\phi$	$r\theta$	r	\emptyset
3	0, 5-○	30	0	Estimation				1.99	0.99	0.17	1.05
				Trimble	0	0	0.0 + 0	2.0	1.0	0.0	1.0
4	○	30	0	Estimation				4.86	8.14	0.22	4.41
				Trimble	0.75	30	0.0 + 0	11.29	7.82	0.0	6.37
5	○	30	0	Estimation				29.3	32.19	1.97	21.15
				Trimble	0.5	30	0.0 + 0	28.38	17.64	0.0	15.34
6	○	30	3	Estimation				52.35	42.97	2.96	32.76
				Trimble	0.5	30	0.0 + 0	51.39	29.4	18.4	33.06
7	∞	30	0	Estimation				1.99	0.99	0.17	1.05
				Trimble	0	0	0.0 + 0	2.0	1.0	0.0	1.0
8	∞	30	10	Estimation				5.26	2.62	0.16	2.68
				Trimble	0	0	0.0 + 0	5.28	2.64	0.0	2.64
9	∞	30	0	Estimation				2.97	1.71	8.3	4.32
				Trimble	0	0	0.07 + 0	2.97	1.69	8.38	4.35
10	∞	30	0	Estimation				2.03	1.72	0.17	1.31
				Trimble	0	0	0.0 + 4	2.25	2.57	0.0	1.61
11	∞	3	0	Estimation				3.01	0.99	6.23	3.41
				Trimble	0	0	0.0 + -1	2.44	1.0	4.08	2.51

Tab. 6.3: Simulation with one kite

The general tests 1, 2, 3, 7 and 8 are intended to test the performance of the estimation in different flight maneuvers. Test one and two is a upward (1) and sideways (2) movement on a constant tether length of 100m. The T-Pos is suppressed after half of the maneuver, but the I-Traj ends in the zenith (1) and forms a whole circle (2). The estimator works as expected and predicts E-Pos correctly based on the last angular velocity. Also in more complex flight maneuvers, such as a circle (3), a figure of eight without and with constant tether reel out speed (7 (Fig. 6.16a), 8 (Fig. 6.16b)), the E-Traj is almost identical to T-Traj. In Fig. 6.16a, the horizontal and vertical offset of T-Pos can be seen, which is $\approx 1.15^\circ$ in vertical direction and $\approx 0.6^\circ$ in horizontal direction.

Fig. 6.16: Test cases 7 and 8

The tests with suppressed data 4, 5 and 6 are intended to analyze the behavior of the estimator in the case, that no position data is received anymore. As described in test 1 and 2, the estimator predicts a constant arc-length derivate and reel out speed. In test 4 (Fig. 6.17a) and 5 (Fig. 6.17b), there is no reel out speed and T-Pos is suppressed after 75% (50%) of the full circle. As expected, the kite keeps flying upwards (sideways) at a constant tether length and velocity. Test 6 (Fig. 6.17c) has a tether reel out speed of $3 \frac{m}{s}$. With constant reel out speed, the estimation of the kite distance is very good (RMSE of 2.9 in test case 6). But in general, it can be seen, that no position data for a longer period leads to a very inaccurate position (RMSE of 32,76m in test case 6). Taking the steering input into account could significantly increase the accuracy of the estimator, because there is a correlation between steering input and rate of turn as described by Jehle (2012).

(a) Test case 4

(b) Test case 5

(c) Test case 6

Fig. 6.17: Test cases 4 to 6

The tests with noise 9, 10 and 11 shall test the behavior of the kite in case of noise. This can either Gaussian noise, errors or packet loss. Test 9 (Fig. 6.18) shows a simulation with high Gaussian noise (7%). It can be seen that the T-Pos data has gaps and sharp edges, where the noise changes. The E-Pos on the other hand corrects these edges and has a smooth trajectory, which adjusts to the new position fast. The RMSE of E-Traj is slightly lower than T-Traj. This can better be seen in test 11 (Fig. 6.19b), where a zero position is sent at the beginning. The reel out speed, which is calculated for the first time step is very high ($\frac{(100m-0m)}{0.05s} = 2000\frac{m}{s}$) and causes the estimated trajectory to overshoot the I-Traj, but it rapidly aligns with I-Traj in a highly damped oscillation. This type of alignment can also be seen in test 10 (Fig. 6.19a), where two errors are included in the T-Traj. These errors affect E-Traj. The peaks have lower amplitude but E-Traj takes longer to align with I-Traj after the error. All in all the RMSE of E-Traj (1.31 m) is lower than the one of T-Traj (1.61 m).

Fig. 6.18: Test Case 9

(a) Test case 10

(b) Test case 11

Fig. 6.19: Test case 10 and 11

6.3.2 Simulation with two kite positions

For the following simulations, two kite positions are sent to the SystemStateEstimator, which represent XSens (X-Pos) and Trimble (T-Pos) position data. The weights for the estimation are:

$$\vec{\alpha}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{0,Trimble} \\ \alpha_{0,XSens} \\ \alpha_{0,Angular} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 \\ 0.1 \\ 0.0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\beta = 0.4$$

As for the other tests, the starting tether length r_0 is 100m. The detailed results can be found in Tab. 6.4.

#	Fig.	t [s]	v_t [$\frac{m}{s}$]	Position	inactive from [$\frac{\% \text{ cycle time}}{100}$]	for [s]	Noise	RMSE [m]			
								$r\phi$	$r\theta$	r	\emptyset
12	∞	30	0	Estimation				0.99	0.16	0.17	0.44
				XSens	0	0	0.0 + 0	4.0	4.0	0.0	2.66
				Trimble	0	0	0.0 + 0	2.0	1.0	0.0	1.0
13	∞	30	0	Estimation				0.99	0.67	0.42	0.69
				XSens	0	0	0.07 + 0	6.22	3.41	22.76	10.79
				Trimble	0	0	0.05 + 0	1.18	1.07	4.62	2.29
14	$0.5 \cdot \infty$	30	0	Estimation				1.27	1.71	0.16	1.04
				XSens	0	0	0.0 + 4	4.75	5.36	0.0	3.37
				Trimble	0	0	0.0 + 4	2.47	3.49	0.0	1.99
15	∞	30	0	Estimation				1.13	0.35	0.17	0.55
				XSens	0.75	3	0.0 + 0	4.44	4.32	0.0	2.92
				Trimble	0	0	0.0 + 0	2.0	1.0	0.0	1.0
16	∞	30	5	Estimation				1.79	0.29	0.16	0.75
				XSens	0	0	0.0 + 0	7.2	7.2	0.0	4.8
				Trimble	0	0	0.0 + 0	3.6	1.8	0.0	1.8
17	∞	30	5	Estimation				2.15	1.61	0.83	1.53
				XSens	0	0	0.07 + 0	5.29	9.59	8.81	7.9
				Trimble	0	0	0.05 + 0	3.61	3.25	1.54	2.8
18	∞	30	5	Estimation				2.69	1.17	0.16	1.34
				XSens	0.5	10	0.0 + 0	19.03	28.63	16.72	21.46
				Trimble	0	0	0.0 + 0	3.6	1.8	0.0	1.8
19	∞	30	5	Estimation				3.95	3.21	0.37	2.51
				XSens	0.5	10	0.0 + 0	19.03	28.63	16.72	21.46
				Trimble	0.75	5	0.0 + 0	12.41	5.25	5.93	7.87
20	$3 \cdot \infty$	30	5	Estimation				5.84	2.84	3.88	4.19
				XSens	0	0	0.01 + 0	16.85	15.46	6.68	13.0
				Trimble	0	0	0.02 + 0	10.33	6.26	5.73	7.44
21	$3 \cdot \infty$	30	5	Estimation				10.48	15.81	13.6	13.3
				XSens	0	0	0.04 + 0	9.22	8.04	28.23	15.16
				Trimble	0	0.05	0.02 - 4	9.17	9.65	11.98	10.27

Tab. 6.4: Simulation with two kites

The general tests 12 and 16 show the behavior of the estimator when it uses two different position data sets. Test 12 (Fig. 6.20a) and 16 (Fig. 6.20b) show the trajectory of one figure of eight (X-Traj, T-Traj and E-Traj). It shows that the weights are implemented correctly. Fig. 6.20b shows that the amplitude of the figure of eight rises with the tether length. This is intended because this is how the current autopilot 3LAP controls the kite; it takes the reflection of the kite to the unit sphere, which is nothing else than scaling the kite distance. So this is how the kite flies in reality.

Fig. 6.20: Test case 12 and 16

The tests with suppressed data 15, 18 and 19 shall test the estimation in case of position data loss. In test 15 (Fig. 6.21a) and 19 (Fig. 6.21c), the X-Pos data is suppressed for 3 s (10 s). E-Traj aligns with T-Traj very fast after the suppression, which results in a small bump in E-Traj. Adjusting the estimation weights can change the speed of alignment. Increasing the weight on the last estimated position will decrease the sensitivity to extreme position changes. The RMSE of E-Traj is lower than the ones of T-Traj and X-Traj in both tests (see Tab. 6.3). This means that the E-Traj is closer to the real trajectory I-Traj than the other trajectories.

In test 19 (Fig. 6.21c), first X-Pos is suppressed after 50% of the full cycle for 10 s and then T-Pos after 75% for 5 s. The estimator still gives a sufficient result, and with a RMSE of 2.51 m, E-Traj is very close to the ideal trajectory I-Traj, even though it receives only one position data for 10s and no position data for 5 s. Th the same time, the differences of T-Traj (RMSE 7.87 m) and X-Traj (RMSE 21.46 m) are much higher.

(a) Test case 15

(b) Test case 18

(c) Test case 19

Fig. 6.21: Test case 15, 18 and 19

The tests with noise 13,14 and 17 show the behavior of the estimator if there is noise in X-Pos and T-Pos. The simulated Gaussian noise of one sensor has a lower effect on the estimator compared to the simulation with one kite. This can be seen in test 13 (Fig. 6.22a) and 17 (Fig. 6.22c). The RMSE (Tab. 6.3) shows that E-Traj (RMSE of 0.69 m and 1.04 m) is much closer to the real trajectory than X-Traj (RMSE of 10.79m and 3.37 m) and T-Traj (RMSE of 2.29m and 1.99 m). The reaction of E-Traj on errors (test case 14 (Fig. 6.22b)) is similar to the behavior with one kite. The outliers have lower amplitude and the E-Traj is smoother.

(a) Test case 13

(b) Test case 14

(c) Test case 17

Fig. 6.22: Test case 13, 14 and 17

The tests with multiple figures 20 and 21 shall simulate a whole power phase for one cycle. Both tests take 30 s per figure leading to a simulation time of 1.5 min. Test 20 (Fig. 6.23a) has Gaussian noise ($X_Pos = 2\%$, $T_Pos = 1\%$). Nevertheless the E-Traj is very close to the real trajectory I-Traj (RMSE = 4.19 m). According to the former test results, it happens that T-Pos is only send three out of four times. Test 21 (Fig. 6.23b) simulates the behavior of the estimator in these situations. The RMSE of E-Traj (13.3 m) is higher than the one of T-Traj (10.27 m), which shows us that E-Traj is further away from I-Traj. Looking at the figure also shows that E-Traj is not smooth. In the time steps when T is suppressed, E-Traj only gets the X-Pos and tries to align with it, whereas in the next time step, when T-Pos is available again, the E-Pos jumps back to a position, which is closer to T-Traj.

Fig. 6.23: Test case 20 and 21

6.3.3 Conclusion

The estimator delivers good results for most test cases. Gaussian noise, errors and packet losses are corrected and the estimated trajectory is smooth. Short periods of sensor data loss (5-10 s) can be bypassed. Otherwise, the E-Pos is not close to the real position anymore. Fig. 6.24 shows that the RMSE of E-Traj is mostly lower than the ones of T-Traj and X-Traj.

Important to mention is that the estimator has a small RMSE in the kite distance even if it is constant (see test 3-5, 7 and 9-15 in Tab. 6.3). A real time analysis of the SystemStateEstimator showed that this inaccuracy is caused by different back and forth transformations into other reference frames of the values. If the estimator is running with two positions, one position is suppressed and the E-Traj aligns with the trajectory of the remaining sensor very fast, causing a gap in the trajectory (Fig. 6.21a, Fig. 6.21b, Fig. 6.21c) or even a zigzag trajectory (Fig. 6.23b).

So for further improvements of the estimation, the following aspects should be considered:

1. It should be investigated if transformations from or to EAKD cause inaccuracy in the kite distance (whether it is on the Python side or the C++ side).
2. The weight on the last estimated position can be increased in order to delay the reaction to new positions, which leads to a smoother trajectory on the one side, but also delivers a less accurate position.
3. The steering input as a basis to estimate the current velocities has the potential to significantly increase the accuracy of the estimation.

Fig. 6.24: Rooted mean square errors of the simulated tests in meter

6.4 Kite State Estimator Test on 2013/21/01

This section shows the results of the measurement that could be harvested during the test on the 21st of January 2013 from 17:00 to 17:30 o'clock. A statement about the behavior of the autopilot, which is flying with the estimated position, cannot be made because of an error in the transformation of the measurements. The measurement data of 30 minutes was replayed in the lab afterwards, and the estimated kite state was recorded. In this case, the RMSE is not a sufficient approach to validate the accuracy of the Estimation, because the real position is unknown. It is possible to compare the positions with the tether length, as it was done to compare different GNSS sensors. But this method would result in a RMSE of 0 for the angular sensor position, because this position is based on the tether length. This would lead to the impression that the angular sensor position is always closest to the real position, which is doubtful. According to recent tests, the Trimble position is the most accurate position in most situations. However, an objective optical analysis gives indications about the quality of the positions. For example the physical properties of a kite do not allow a 180° turn within a 20th of a second. The kite turns rather smooth. The tests that were performed show a figure of eight at a relative time of 2593 s until 2619 s. The time between two symbols is one second ($\Delta t = 1$ s) and the vertical and horizontal arc length is equal to $r\phi$ and $r\theta$ in ARC_{EG} coordinates. This allows to show a 3D trajectory in a 2D plot that includes elevation ϕ , azimuth θ and tether length r .

It can definitely be said, that the XSens trajectory is the worst during the figure of eight that is shown in the real test 1 in Fig. 6.25.

Fig. 6.25: Real flight test No 1. $\Delta t = 1s$, $x = r\theta$, $y = r\phi$

On the other hand, the angular sensor position and the Trimble position are smoother and very close to each other. This is a clear indication that the real position is close to their position. Angular and Trimble position have a weight of 70% percent for this estimation, which is the reason why the wrong XSens data does not have a significant effect on the estimation. This can also be seen in real test 8 (Fig. 6.26).

Fig. 6.26: Real flight test No 8. $\Delta t = 1s$, $x = r\theta$, $y = r\phi$

But although the XSens has only 10% weight, it has an impact on the estimated trajectory. There is a small gap at the first down turn on the left side, shortly after the XSens position is suppressed. This effect is more extreme if the Trimble sensor fails, because it has a weight of 50%. This can be seen in real test 4 (Fig. 6.27), 6 (Fig. 6.28) and 7 (Fig. 6.29), where the estimated trajectory jumps extremely after the Trimble position was suppressed.

Fig. 6.27: Real flight test No 4. $\Delta t = 1s$, $x = r\theta$, $y = r\phi$

Fig. 6.28: Real flight test No 6. $\Delta t = 1s$, $x = r\theta$, $y = r\phi$

Fig. 6.29: Real flight test No 7. $\Delta t = 1s$, $x = r\theta$, $y = r\phi$

This phenomenon was also regarded during the simulations. This is a very rare extreme situation and the author decided to keep the variables of the estimator as they are. The advantage of the estimation can be seen in real test number 3 (Fig. 6.30).

Fig. 6.30: Real flight test No 3. $\Delta t = 1\text{s}$, $x = r\theta$, $y = r\phi$

The estimator runs only with angular data and the estimation position is much smoother. This will theoretically lead to a better performance of the autopilot, because the kite state is more consistent. However, this is still speculative, because it has not been tested so far.

6.5 Summary

Finally, the tests that were performed have an outcome that the angular sensors and the estimator fulfill the requirements. The angular sensors deliver very accurate data, but with a time delay of about 200ms compared to the GNSS position. The tether sag and drag forces on the tether cause this delay. It is possible to correct this delay by an appropriate prediction method or a tether model. One empirical tether model based on the assessment of the data and simple aerodynamic relations was presented. The parameters for this model were calculated based on the given test data. The correction gives impressive results, but it can not be used as a general correction method because it is not fully validated and it cannot be assumed that the parameters that are derived from a 30 min dataset are universally valid. A correlation between the offset that causes the time delay and the tether length could not be shown with the test data. This fact should be further examined because the drag force rises with rising area of the tether according to Aglietti (2009). The double exponential smoothing prediction (DESP) algorithm can be used to compensate the time delay by predicting into the future. But for the first tests of the Kite State Estimation, the author decided to take the raw angular data. The real flight showed that the System State Estimator works as expected, but extreme situations show the limits of the estimator. If there is a big error and one position is suppressed periodically, the estimated position goes back and forth towards the remaining position, which results in a zigzag trajectory. The simulation shows the same results. The Kite State Estimator can correct Gaussian noise very good. The Kite State Estimator works as expected and is, in combination with the angular sensors, a valuable addition to the GNSS position sensors. There is still space for improvements such as adding the steering input to the calculation of the arc length derivatives. Also an automated calibration of the angular sensors could be added. But the test results show that the DESP algorithm makes the kite state more reliable. Even if the fusion algorithm runs with one sensor alone. But the best results could be archived by using angular sensors and the Trimble GNSS.

7 Outlook and Conclusion

It is clear that wind energy will play an important role in the field of renewable energy. New techniques, such as AWE in particular, have the potential to lead the way to a wind energy revolution. However, until now, the development of these systems is not finished and a lot of challenges have to be accomplished, before AWE energy can become competitive with conventional energy generation. Many AWE concepts struggle to determine the position of their flying device, especially during highly dynamic flight situations. Most GNSS sensors are not designed to be attached to a kite and determine its position at an accuracy that is needed for reliable automatic control of the kite. GNSS sensor positions alone are not sufficient for reliable automated kite control systems.

The aim of this thesis was to enhance the position estimation of the kite. The author decided to attach additional sensors at the ground to measure the elevation and azimuth angle of the tether which holds the kite. The sensors were embedded in a solid aluminum and stainless steel construction that exceeds its requirements (see Chapter 4). A new position was calculated with the data from these sensors and the kite distance. The assessment of the first flight test data showed that angular sensors are generally usable to estimate the position of a fast moving kite. The test showed that there is an offset to the position that was measured by the GNSS sensors, which can be basically compensated by a time shift of 200ms. Without compensation, the azimuth and elevation positions were very accurate (error $< 0.7^\circ$) during high force phases ($>2000\text{N}$) but not very exact (error sometimes $> 5^\circ$) with low force on the tether. A realistic tether model is needed to determine a reliable position that is only based on angular sensors. Without a tether model, the GNSS sensors deliver a very accurate position during low force phases. The author fused the GNSS data with the angular data to determine a reliable position. He chose to implement and test the double exponential smoothing prediction (DESP) algorithm for the fusion. The simulations and the real tests showed that the estimated position was more accurate than any single position and the DESP can compensate Gaussian noise, errors and even sensor failures up to a certain degree (see Section 6.3). The new features were integrated in the existing software structure and graphical user interface. Based on this work it is possible to build a reliable, automated kite control system.

Further developments of the presented kite state estimation are possible. The estimation could be extended with additional position information coming from other sensors. The performance of a differential GPS sensor in kite power applications should be assessed. A tether model that really fits to the physical world would also be an important improvement. Pre-investigations that create a solid basis for such a development have been done (see Eq. 6.1 and Eq. 6.2). Sliding contacts would be a very practical addition for the angular sensors. This would ensure that the safety link for the elevation sensor never breaks. The autopilot performance with the kite state estimator should be further examined. In general, one high performance GNSS sensor at the kite and angular sensors with a DESP fusion algorithm are sufficient for reliable control of AWE kite wings, but it should be investigated whether an orientation sensor, combined with angular sensors and a low-cost GNSS sensor, is also

7 Outlook and Conclusion

sufficient for a reliable control system. However, AWE will play an important role for energy generation after all problems have been solved. Solving the challenges one by one will lead to a reliable low carbon energy production of a new generation.

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Annex

Absolute Drehgeber – Singleturn

Kompakt, magnetisch

Sendix 3651 / 3671 (Welle / Hohlwelle)

Analog

Die Sendix 3651 und Sendix 3671 Singleturn mit analoger Schnittstelle und magnetischer Sensorik sind aufgrund ihrer vielfältigen Schnittstellen und Messbereiche besonders flexibel einsetzbar. Eine grüne und rote LED erleichtern als Referenzpunkt und als Fehleranzeige sowohl die Installation als auch die Fehlerdiagnose.

Geschützt bis IP69K, schockfest und resistent gegen extreme Temperaturschwankungen, eignen sich die Sendix selbst für anspruchsvolle Außeneinsätze.

Diese Drehgeber verfügen über eine e1-Zulassung durch das Kraftfahrt-Bundesamt (KBA).

Sicherer Einsatz

- Berührungsloses Messsystem für eine verschleißfreie und langlebige Anwendung
- Stabiles Druckgussgehäuse und IP Schutz bis 69k für besondere Dichtigkeit
- Hohe Schockfestigkeit und Vibrationsfestigkeit für besondere Widerstandsfähigkeit

Kompakt und leistungsstark

- Außendurchmesser von nur 36 mm
- In Hohlwellenausführung findet eine Sackloch-Hohlwelle von bis zu 10 mm Platz, die sich individuell – über Drehmomentstütze oder Statorcupplung - befestigen lässt.
- 360° aufgelöst in 4096 unterschiedliche Positionen
- Für den Einsatz in 12 V oder 24 V Automobil-Bordnetzen

Safety-Lockplus™

Flanschseitig IP69k, robuste Lagerbaugruppen mit verblockten Lagern, mechanisch geschützte Wellendichtung

Sensor-Protect™

Vollvergossene Elektronik, getrennte mechanische Baugruppe

Bestellschlüssel Welle

8.3651 . 2XXX . XXXX
Typ a b c d e f g h

Wird für einen Drehgeber zu jedem Parameter die unterstrichene Vorzugsoption gewählt, beträgt die Lieferzeit 10 Arbeitstage für max. 10 Stück pro Lieferung. Mengen bis zu 50 Stück dieser Typen haben eine Regellieferzeit von 15 Arbeitstagen.

<p>a Flansch 2 = <u>Synchroflansch</u></p> <p>b Welle (ø x L), mit Fläche 3 = <u>ø 6 x 12,5 mm</u> 5 = ø 6,35 (1/4") x 12,5 mm 6 = ø 8 x 12,5 mm</p>	<p>c Ausgangsschaltung ²⁾ 3 = <u>Stromausgang</u> 4 = <u>Spannungsausgang</u></p> <p>d Anschlussart 1 = Kabel axial (1 m PUR) 2 = <u>Kabel radial (1 m PUR)</u> 3 = M12-Stecker axial 4 = M12-Stecker radial</p>	<p>e Messbereich 1 = 1 x 360° 2 = 1 x 180° 3 = 1 x 90° 4 = 1 x 45°</p> <p>f Ausgang / Versorgungsspannung 3 = 4 ... <u>20 mA / 10 ... 30 V DC</u> 4 = 0 ... <u>10 V / 15 ... 30 V DC</u> 5 = 0 ... 5 V / 10 ... 30 V DC</p>	<p>g Option 1 1 = <u>Zählweise cw</u> ¹⁾ 2 = Zählweise ccw ¹⁾</p> <p>h Option 2 1 = <u>IP67</u> 2 = IP69K</p> <p><i>optional auf Anfrage</i> - Ex 2/22 - seewasserfest - Kabel-Sonderlänge</p>
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Bestellschlüssel Hohlwelle

8.3671 . XXXX . XXXX
Typ a b c d e f g h

Wird für einen Drehgeber zu jedem Parameter die unterstrichene Vorzugsoption gewählt, beträgt die Lieferzeit 10 Arbeitstage für max. 10 Stück pro Lieferung. Mengen bis zu 50 Stück dieser Typen haben eine Regellieferzeit von 15 Arbeitstagen.

<p>a Flansch 2 = mit Drehmomentstütze 5 = <u>mit Statorcupplung</u></p> <p>b Hohlwelle 2 = <u>ø 6 mm</u> 3 = ø 6,35 mm (1/4") 4 = ø 8 mm 6 = ø 10 mm</p>	<p>c Ausgangsschaltung ²⁾ 3 = <u>Stromausgang</u> 4 = <u>Spannungsausgang</u></p> <p>d Anschlussart 1 = Kabel axial (1 m PUR) 2 = <u>Kabel radial (1 m PUR)</u> 3 = M12-Stecker axial 4 = M12-Stecker radial</p>	<p>e Messbereich 1 = 1 x 360° 2 = 1 x 180° 3 = 1 x 90° 4 = 1 x 45°</p> <p>f Ausgang / Versorgungsspannung 3 = 4 ... <u>20 mA / 10 ... 30 V DC</u> 4 = 0 ... <u>10 V / 15 ... 30 V DC</u> 5 = 0 ... 5 V / 10 ... 30 V DC</p>	<p>g Option 1 1 = <u>Zählweise cw</u> ¹⁾ 2 = Zählweise ccw ¹⁾</p> <p>h Option 2 1 = <u>IP67</u> 2 = IP69K</p> <p><i>optional auf Anfrage</i> - Ex 2/22 - seewasserfest - Kabel-Sonderlänge</p>
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1) cw = aufsteigende Positionswerte bei Drehung der Welle im Uhrzeigersinn, mit Blick auf die Welle.

2) Ausgangsschaltung "3" nur in Verbindung mit Ausgang "3", Ausgangsschaltung "4" nur in Verbindung mit Ausgang "4" oder "5"

Absolute Drehgeber – Singleturn

Kompakt, magnetisch	Sendix 3651 / 3671 (Welle / Hohlwelle)	Analog
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Montagezubehör für Wellen-Drehgeber

Kupplung	Balgkupplung ø 19 mm für Welle 6 mm	8.0000.1101.0606
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Montagezubehör für Hohlwellen-Drehgeber

Zylinderstift, lang für Drehmomentstütze		Mit Befestigungsgewinde	8.0010.4700.0000
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Anschlussstechnik

Selbstkonfektionierbarer Steckverbinder	M12	8.0000.5116.0000
Vorkonfektionierter Kabelsatz mit 2 m PVC-Kabel	M12	05.WAKS4.5-2/P00

Weiteres Zubehör finden Sie im Kapitel Zubehör oder im Bereich Zubehör unter: www.kuebler.com/zubehoer.
 Weitere Anschlussstechnik finden Sie im Kapitel Anschlussstechnik oder im Bereich Anschlussstechnik unter: www.kuebler.com/anschlussstechnik.

Mechanische Kennwerte	
Max. Drehzahl	6000 min ⁻¹
Anlaufdrehmoment	< 0,06 Nm
Wellenbelastbarkeit	radial 40 N axial 20 N
Gewicht	ca. 0,2 kg
Schutzart EN 60 529/DIN 40050-9	IP67 / IP69k
Zulassung Explosionsschutz	optional Zone 2 und 22
Arbeitstemperaturbereich	-40°C ... +85°C
Werkstoffe	Welle / Hohlwelle nicht rostender Stahl Flansch Aluminium Gehäuse Zink-Druckgussgehäuse Kabel PUR
Schockfestigkeit nach EN 60068-2-27	5000 m/s ² , 6 ms
Vibrationsfestigkeit nach EN 60068-2-6	300 m/s ² , 10 ... 2000 Hz
Dauerschocken nach EN 60068-2-27	1000 m/s ² , 2 ms
Vibration (Breitbandrauschen) n. EN 60068-2-64	5 ... 2500 Hz, 100 m/s ² - rms

Allgemeine elektrische Angaben	
RoHS-konform gemäß	EG-Richtlinie 2002/95/EG
CE-konform gemäß	EN 61000-6-2, EN 61000-6-4, EN 61000-6-3 und EN 61000-4-8 (Verhalten bei magnetischer Beeinflussung)
e1-konform gemäß	EG-Richtlinie 2009/19/EG (nach Normen EN 55025, ISO 11452 und ISO 7637)

Elektrische Kennwerte Stromschnittstelle 4 ... 20 mA	
Sensor	
Versorgungsspannung	10 ... 30 V DC
Stromaufnahme (ohne Last)	max. 38 mA
Verpolschutz der Versorgungsspannung	ja
Messbereich	45°, 90°, 180° oder 360°
Auflösung	12 bit
Linearität	< 1° (360° Messbereich)
Wiederholgenauigkeit (25°C)	< 0,1° (360° Messbereich)
Status-LED	Rot Unterbrechung Stromschleife, Bürde am Eingang zu groß. Grün Referenzpunktanzeige leuchtet bei cw: zw. 0° und 1° bei ccw: zw. 0° und -1°
Stromschleife	
Bürde am Ausgang	max. 200 Ohm bei 10 V DC max. 900 Ohm bei 24 V DC
Einschwingzeit	< 1 ms (R _{last} = 400 Ohm, 25°C)
Kurzschlussfester Ausgang	
Bei korrekt angelegter Versorgungsspannung. Aber nicht Ausgang gegen +U _B . Versorgungsspannung und Sensorausgangssignal sind nicht galvanisch getrennt.	

Elektrische Kennwerte Spannungsschnittstelle	
Sensor	
Versorgungsspannung	Ausgang 0 ... 5 V 10 ... 30 V DC Ausgang 0 ... 10 V 15 ... 30 V DC
Stromaufnahme (ohne Last)	max. 35 mA
Verpolschutz der Versorgungsspannung	ja
Messbereich	45°, 90°, 180° oder 360°
Auflösung	12 bit
Linearität	< 1° (360° Messbereich)
Wiederholgenauigkeit (25°C)	< 0,1° (360° Messbereich)
Spannungsausgang	
Ausgangsstrom	max. 10 mA
Einschwingzeit	< 1 ms (R _{last} ≥ 1 KOhm, 25°C)
Kurzschlussfester Ausgang	
Bei korrekt angelegter Versorgungsspannung. Aber nicht Ausgang gegen +U _B . Versorgungsspannung und Sensorausgangssignal sind nicht galvanisch getrennt.	
Status-LED	Grün Referenzpunktanzeige leuchtet bei cw: zw. 0° und 1° bei ccw: zw. 0° und -1°

Absolute Drehgeber – Singleturn

Kompakt, magnetisch

Sendix 3651 / 3671 (Welle / Hohlwelle)

Analog

Beispiel (Verlauf des Ausgangssignals)

Messbereich 45° / 90° / 180° / 360°

Variante cw

Variante ccw

Anschlussbelegung

Stromschnittstelle

Signal	0V	+U _B	+I	-I
Kabelfarbe	WH	BN	GN	YE
M12 / Pin	3	2	4	5

Spannungsschnittstelle

Signal	0V	+U _B	+U ₀	-U ₀
Kabelfarbe	WH	BN	GN	YE
M12 / Pin	3	2	4	5

Absolute Drehgeber – Singleturn

Kompakt, magnetisch **Sendix 3651 / 3671 (Welle / Hohlwelle)** **Analog**

Maßbilder Wellenausführung

Synchroflansch, \varnothing 36 mm

1 M3, 6 [0,24] tief

1 M3, 6 [0,24] tief

Maßbilder Hohlwellenausführung

Mit Drehmomentstütze, \varnothing 36 mm

1 Nut Drehmomentstütze,
Empfehlung: Zylinderstift nach DIN 7, \varnothing 4 mm

Mit Statorkupplung, \varnothing 36 mm

EL3068 | 8-Kanal-Analog-Eingangsklemme 0...10 V, single-ended, 12 Bit

Die analoge Eingangsklemme EL3068 verarbeitet Signale im Bereich von 0 bis 10 V. Mit einer Auflösung von 12 Bit wird die Spannung digitalisiert und galvanisch getrennt zum übergeordneten Automatisierungsgerät transportiert. Die EtherCAT-Klemme EL3068 vereint acht Kanäle in einem Gehäuse. Die Powerkontakte sind durchverbunden; die Bezugsmasse der Eingänge ist der 0-V-Powerkontakt. Der Signalzustand der EtherCAT-Klemme wird durch Leuchtdioden angezeigt.

Technische Daten	EL3068 ES3068
Anzahl Eingänge	8 (single-ended)
Spannungsversorgung	über den E-Bus
Technik	single-ended
Signalspannung	0...10 V
Distributed-Clocks	–
Innenwiderstand	> 130 kΩ
Grenzfrequenz Eingangsfiler	1 kHz
Wandlungszeit	1,25 ms voreingestellt, konfigurierbar
Auflösung	12 Bit (16 Bit Darstellung, inkl. Vorzeichen)
Messfehler	< ±0,3 % (bezogen auf den Messbereichsendwert)
Potenzialtrennung	500 V (E-Bus/Signalspannung)
Stromaufn. Powerkontakte	–
Stromaufnahme E-Bus	130 mA typ.
Spannungsfestigkeit	max. 30 V
Breite im Prozessabbild	Inputs: 32 Byte
Besondere Eigenschaften	FIR-/IIR-Filter aktivierbar, Grenzwertüberwachung
Gewicht	ca. 60 g
Betriebs-/Lagertemperatur	0...+55 °C/-25...+85 °C
Relative Feuchte	95 % ohne Betauung
Schwingungs-/Schockfestigkeit	gemäß EN 60068-2-6/EN 60068-2-27
EMV-Festigkeit/-Aussendung	gemäß EN 61000-6-2/EN 61000-6-4
Schutzart/Einbaulage	IP 20/beliebig
Steckbare Verdrahtung	bei allen ESxxxx-Klemmen
Zulassungen	CE, UL, Ex